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Assessment of Medium-Term Water Stress in the Gürbe Catchment (Switzerland) under Climate Change Scenarios

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Abstract

This study evaluates medium-term water stress in the Gürbe catchment (Switzerland) for the period 2045–2074 under three climate change scenarios using the Water Stress Index (WSI). Employing CH2018 climate projections and using hydrological modeling data, the research estimates future water availability and demand across agriculture, drinking water, industry, and ecology. Results indicate increasing demand for irrigation and drinking water due to rising temperatures, reduced summer precipitation, and population growth, while summer streamflow is projected to decline. Under the RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios, average WSI values in July and August are expected to surpass moderate stress levels, with some individual months potentially experiencing significantly higher stress. Insights from interviews on the summer droughts of 2018 and 2022 reveal key challenges for local water management stakeholders, including stress on fluvial ecosystems and accelerated peat degradation on the valley floor. The findings underscore the need for effective water resource management strategies to mitigate climate-induced shifts in water availability and demand in the Gürbetal region.

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Foreword

Personal Motivation

My personal motivation for writing this thesis stems from several factors. My love of water and its multifaceted nature has always shaped my choice of thesis / final assignment topics.

During the hot summers of 2018 and 2022, I followed with great interest and concern the increasing reports of local water shortages, the efforts being made to remedy them, and the voices from all corners of water users who claimed they had never experienced a similar situation. Suddenly, climate change seemed more tangible than ever as an imminent threat to Switzerland's much-vaunted water tower. Inevitably, I also wondered how the "normal" would change—were the past hot and dry summers giving us a glimpse of the normal of the future through the occurrence of today's extremes, or had we just experienced the transition to that very future, which in turn would mean new extremes of tomorrow?

In order to approach these questions on a scientific level, I decided to write a thesis in the field of hydrology, dealing with drought and hydrological projections. I was inspired by a seminar by Dr Marianne Milano, where we had to write a thesis based on three interviews with water management stakeholders on a hydrological hotspot. I was also interested in a publication by Dr Milano in which she examines the monthly water consumption rates in several catchments in the Canton of Vaud and their future development. Methodologically and thematically, I found this approach very exciting and decided to write my Master's thesis on this topic. In order to maintain a tangible link to the area under study, I decided in a preliminary discussion with Dr Milano to study a single catchment area in the Canton of Berne and to put the results into perspective by interviewing selected local water management stakeholders. Prof Dr Bettina Schäfli agreed to supervise my work.

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Conversion Table

Table 1: Conversion of the water depth in millimetres over the entire catchment area into the corresponding total volume of water in cubic meters.

mm catchment-wide	m³
10	1'160'000
20	2'320'000
50	5'800'000
75	8'700'000
100	11'600'000
150	17'400'000

1 Introduction

European temperatures have risen faster than the global average, particularly in northern and eastern Europe during winter and in southern Europe during summer, leading to more frequent heatwaves. Precipitation patterns have shifted, with decreases in southern Europe and increases in the north, trends expected to persist. Snow cover and glaciers are diminishing, particularly at altitudes below 1500–2000 meters, with permafrost continuing to thaw (IPCC, 2022).

In northern Europe, warmer winters and increased precipitation have led to higher annual streamflow, although spring and summer streamflow are decreasing due to earlier snowmelt. Southern Europe, by contrast, has seen reductions in streamflow due to less precipitation and higher evapotranspiration rates. These trends also observed in some parts of eastern Europe. These changes have resulted in a pan-European pattern of increased winter streamflow and decreased summer streamflow, though regional exceptions exist. The impacts of these hydrological shifts are complicated by human activities like damming and water abstraction for agriculture (Stahl et al., 2010). Projections indicate that northern and central Europe will experience increased winter streamflow, while southern Europe will see further reductions, particularly during the summer months, intensifying water stress and competition for resources (European Commission, 2020a; IPCC, 2023).

Droughts and water stress are anticipated to become more severe and frequent, particularly in southern and central Europe, as precipitation decreases and temperatures rise. Water-stressed regions, including the Mediterranean, face challenges in sustaining agriculture, domestic water supplies, and industrial needs. If global warming exceeds 3°C, water scarcity in southern Europe will reach "very high" levels, while at 2°C warming, desertification will threaten 8% of European territory (IPCC, 2022). Past European droughts, such as those in 2003, 2015, 2018, and 2019, demonstrated the serious consequences of such events, including diminished agricultural productivity, environmental damage, and stressed vegetation (Blauhut et al., 2022; García-Herrera et al., 2010; Laaha et al., 2017).

Multinational research initiatives have significantly contributed to understanding droughts and hydrological changes. The FRIEND project, for example, has facilitated cross-regional data sharing to better understand hydrological variability, including droughts and floods. The ARIDE project investigated the characteristics of European droughts and their environmental impacts, while the WATCH project focused on the

global water cycle’s response to climate change by integrating climate and hydrological models. These efforts have been instrumental in assessing how climate change affects Europe’s water resources and ecosystems, advancing scientific knowledge through collaborative international studies (Demuth and Stahl, 1999; Harding et al., 2011; Tallaksen and Van Lanen, 2024).

Figure 1: Projected change in median streamflow (Q_{50}) compared to the baseline period (1981–2010) under a scenario of global temperature rises of (a) 1.5°C, (b) 2°C, and (c) 3°C (Figure from European Commission, 2020a, p. 9).

Switzerland has experienced a significant warming trend over the last century, with average temperatures rising by approximately 2°C—double the global average (Bundesamt für Umwelt BAFU, 2020, p. 30). This has resulted in shifting seasonal patterns, including earlier snowmelt and longer vegetation periods. Projections from the CH2018 climate scenarios indicate that by the end of the century, Switzerland could experience an additional 3–5°C increase in temperature under a high-emissions scenario (RCP8.5), and even under a low-emissions scenario (RCP2.6), warming of 1–2°C is expected. This will lead to milder winters, a significant reduction in snow cover and more frequent replacement of snow by rain at lower altitudes (Bundesamt für Umwelt BAFU, 2020).

In terms of precipitation, the CH2018 scenarios (see NCCS, 2018) forecast a shift in seasonal distribution, with wetter winters and drier summers. These changes will likely increase soil moisture deficits and elevate the risk of summer droughts. Additionally, the frequency of heavy precipitation events is expected to rise in all seasons, intensifying the risks of flooding, landslides, and soil erosion, particularly in mountainous areas where thawing permafrost reduces slope stability (Bundesamt für Umwelt BAFU, 2020). Heatwaves are expected to become more frequent and severe, exacerbating health risks, especially in urban areas due to the heat island

effect (Bundesamt für Umwelt BAFU, 2020). The Canton of Bern, like other regions, faces warming winters, reduced snowfall, and drier summers, which threaten agriculture, tourism, and water resources critical for the region's ecosystems (National Centre for Climate Services NCCS, 2021).

In response, Switzerland has developed adaptation strategies focusing on mitigating climate-related risks and enhancing societal resilience. These include action plans targeting natural hazard management, water, soil, energy, and biodiversity (Bundesamt für Umwelt BAFU, 2020).

Climate change is significantly impacting hydrological processes in Switzerland. Rising temperatures have accelerated the melting of glaciers and snowpacks. Glaciers have historically acted as natural reservoirs, releasing meltwater during summer months. However, their accelerated retreat has created a short-term surge in water flows that will ultimately diminish as glaciers lose mass. This reduction will particularly affect rivers and streams during late summer, which could compromise water resources critical for agriculture, drinking supplies, and hydroelectric power generation (Brunner et al., 2019b; Bundesamt für Umwelt BAFU, 2021). Snow-dominated pre-alpine catchments, which store snow during winter and release meltwater in spring, are also seeing reductions in snow accumulation and earlier snowmelt. This shift is altering seasonal water availability, with peak flows occurring earlier in the year and decreasing water volumes during the summer (Bundesamt für Umwelt BAFU, 2021).

Precipitation patterns are projected to change with increasing winter precipitation combined with a rising zero-degree level. This leads to higher winter runoff, while summer precipitation is decreasing, resulting in prolonged dry spells and higher risks of summer droughts. These trends exacerbate soil moisture deficits and reduce water availability during critical agricultural periods (NCCS, 2018). Reduced summer streamflow is projected at all altitude levels, which will further increase competition for water resources (Brunner et al., 2023).

Groundwater resources in Switzerland, though abundant, are unevenly distributed. Shallow and karst aquifers respond more rapidly to fluctuations in streamflow, leading to temporary drying of springs during drought periods. Climate change is predicted to shift the annual regime of groundwater recharge processes and slightly reduce recharge. This is most pronounced in the summer months due to reduced precipitation and higher evaporation rates. However, the volume of large groundwater bodies is projected to remain constant, provided that the aquifers can be replenished regularly (Bundesamt für Umwelt BAFU, 2021, p. 50). In some alpine regions, groundwater volumes may decrease over time (Bundesamt für Umwelt BAFU, 2021).

The frequency and intensity of hydrological extremes is projected to increase. Floods are becoming more common due to heavy localized rainfall and rapidly melting snow, especially in alpine regions. Conversely, prolonged droughts, driven by higher temperatures and lower precipitation, are also increasing in frequency. This dual threat of flood and drought exacerbates risks to water resources, agriculture, and ecosystem stability (Brunner et al., 2019b).

Switzerland has experienced an increase in drought frequency and severity, a trend expected to worsen with climate change. Hydrological droughts are primarily caused by reduced precipitation, declining snowmelt, and increased evapotranspiration (Brunner et al., 2023). These droughts pose significant risks to agriculture, ecosystems, and water supply systems. High-elevation regions are increasingly prone to snowmelt-deficit droughts, while low-elevation areas are dominated by rainfall-deficit droughts (Brunner et al., 2023). The effects of these droughts are evident, causing severe reductions in streamflow, reduced groundwater recharge, reduced electricity production and stress on aquatic ecosystems (Bundesamt für Umwelt BAFU, 2021, 2019; Lanz, 2021). Alpine catchments are not prone to multiyear droughts (Brunner and Tallaksen, 2019).

Since the turn of the millennium, four drought events occurred in Switzerland. The 2003 drought caused widespread discharge deficits with return periods of up to 50 years in some regions (Brunner et al., 2019c, p. 2318). The 2015 drought was less intense but still notable for its low return periods of up to 10 years. In 2018, north-eastern Switzerland and pre-alpine areas suffered extreme soil moisture deficits and prolonged low streamflow, with soil moisture deficits reaching 100-year return periods in some areas (Brunner et al., 2019c, p. 2321). The 2022 drought stands out as one of the most extreme events in recent Swiss history. Temperatures were 2.3°C above the 1991–2020 norm, and spring and summer precipitation levels were only 60–80% of the usual amounts. The resulting water shortages caused widespread drought conditions, leading to historically low water levels in rivers, lakes, and groundwater. The impacts on aquatic ecosystems were severe, with many small and medium-sized rivers drying up, resulting in increased water temperatures and reduced oxygen levels, which posed significant risks to fish populations, especially trout and grayling (Bundesamt für Umwelt BAFU, 2023; MeteoSchweiz, 2023).

Climate change is exerting substantial pressure on Switzerland's water resource management, particularly in sectors such as agriculture, drinking water, industrial use, and ecology. The changing climate is altering water availability and demand, presenting new challenges for managing these crucial resources. As this thesis is addressing the water demand sectors of irrigation, livestock, industry and drinking water, the projected developments in these sectors are outlined in the following four sections.

Irrigation in Switzerland remains relatively modest compared to neighboring southern countries, with an annual usage of approximately 144 million cubic meters of water for irrigating 55,000 hectares (BLW in Fuhrer and Holzkämper, 2013, p. 34), primarily vegetable crops, grasslands, orchards, and vineyards, particularly in the Valais region. Only 3–4% of Swiss agricultural land is irrigated (Eisenring et al., 2021; Fuhrer and Holzkämper, 2013), although for vegetable crops, this figure rises to 77% (Eisenring et al., 2021). Modeling data suggest that irrigation could increase crop yields for up to 41% of agricultural land (Fuhrer and Jasper, 2009), though costs currently limit its widespread application (Fuhrer and Holzkämper, 2013). As climate change progresses, the demand for irrigation will rise due to increased temperatures, higher evaporation rates, and reduced summer precipitation, leading to more frequent dry spells. By mid-century, irrigation demand for crops such as potatoes and rye grass could increase by 20%, and by 30% by the end of the century (Eisenring et al., 2021).

For example in the Broye region, a nivo-pluvial catchment, water availability may not meet irrigation needs every fifth year under a strong climate change scenario by the 2050 horizon (Fuhrer, 2012). This makes adaptive measures necessary. These include adjusting cultivation methods (e.g., selecting more drought-resistant crops) and improving irrigation infrastructure (Eisenring et al., 2021; Fuhrer and Holzkämper, 2013). Without regulatory measures, agricultural water demand is projected to increase, which could lead to negative environmental impacts and water shortages (Fuhrer and Holzkämper, 2013).

In the Canton of Berne, surface water can be used for irrigation, with temporary abstraction requiring a municipal permit and permanent installations needing cantonal concessions. Residual water requirements have to be fulfilled. Temporary withdrawal constraints can be put in place by cantonal authorities in case of low flow conditions. However, data on irrigation water use are scarce, and neither maximum abstraction limits nor precise volumes of water used are known. To address this, the Swiss government instructed federal and cantonal authorities in 2021 to establish a national agricultural water use database (Pestoni et al., 2023).

While no specific literature addresses future livestock projections in Switzerland, European trends point to declining cattle numbers due to environmental concerns, particularly regarding greenhouse gas emissions. This aligns with a global shift toward poultry and alternative proteins as beef consumption declines (Blair et al., 2024; European Commission, 2020b). Swiss agricultural policies, such as the upcoming "Agrarpolitik 30+" (AP30+), aim to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and may further influence livestock farming practices. A detailed draft of the AP 30+ is expected by 2027 (Bundesamt für Landwirtschaft BLW, 2024).

Drinking water need depends on residential numbers. Switzerland's population is projected to grow by 20% by 2050 under a medium growth scenario, with a 10% increase in the Canton of Bern, concentrated in urban areas (Kanton Bern, 2021). Drinking water is supplied primarily from groundwater and spring sources. Municipalities are supposed to access to two independent water resources (Lanz, 2021). Household water use has decreased in recent years due to more efficient appliances, although virtual water use remains high (Freiburghaus, 2015).

Switzerland's working population is expected to increase overall, though the Canton of Bern may see a 3% decline (Bundesamt für Statistik BFS, 2020). Half of industrial water use is supplied through public networks the other half through their own supplies (Freiburghaus, 2009). Industrial water use currently is greater than household water use, with existing potential to increase water efficiency. Challenges will arise due to periods with low streamflow, which could lead to conflicts with industrial wastewater (Lanz, 2021).

Aquatic ecosystems are highly vulnerable to both human-driven water stress and climate change. Water quality is deteriorating due to reduced phosphate levels and higher concentrations of pharmaceuticals, with river ecosystems showing signs of stress such as lower invertebrate richness and increased algal biomass. Dams exacerbate these effects by disrupting natural flow regimes, making biological communities less resilient (Sabater et al., 2018). Rising water temperatures further threaten cold-water species like trout and grayling, which face stress or even mortality when water temperatures exceed 18°C and 25°C, respectively (Bundesamt für Umwelt BAFU, 2019).

1.1 Synthesis & Research Gap

The review synthesizes a broad range of literature on the hydrological impacts of climate change, focusing particularly on drought and water stress. A clear pattern is observed across Europe, where rising temperatures and shifting precipitation trends are intensifying drought severity, particularly in Southern and Central Europe. In Switzerland, the hydrological cycle is being significantly altered by reduced glacier melt and earlier snowmelt, which are contributing to a decline in summer streamflow.

Although drought has increasingly become a topic of scientific inquiry in Switzerland, with numerous publicly accessible studies on both past extreme events and general hydro-climatic developments, regional studies focused on specific areas are relatively scarce. This could be due to the novelty of drought as an issue in Switzerland, where basic studies have been prioritized over regional research. In addition, regional studies tend to be commissioned by local public bodies from consultancy firms, which limits wider accessibility. Given that hydrological impacts vary according to regional socio-demographic and hydro-climatic conditions, the need for region-specific studies is becoming increasingly important, especially as climate change accelerates.

Publications assessing water stress through supply and demand estimations are limited, both for Switzerland and for the Gürbetal region in particular. Existing studies tend to focus on broader areas or different cantons, such as Vaud and Valais (Milano et al., 2016; Milano and Reynard, 2022). Therefore, this master's thesis will be the first study to investigate the impacts of climate change on the hydrology of the Gürbetal region through a supply and demand approach, and to my knowledge, the first of its kind for any specific region in the Canton of Bern. The Gürbetal is an interesting case study due to its pluvial regime with a strong nival influence, which will change significantly under climate change, and its predominantly agricultural land use with vegetable cultivation on the valley floor. Furthermore, the valley is a rather peripheral region that is often overlooked or not studied separately in larger studies due to its location parallel to the larger Aare valley. For this reason, impending drought processes may remain overlooked.

1.2 Research Objectives & Questions

The principal objective of this Master's thesis is to assess the potential impacts of climate change on water availability and demand in the Gürbe Valley, focusing on both the short-term period from 2020 to 2049 and the medium-term period from 2045 to 2074. To contextualise the results, the expertise of regional water management

stakeholders will be included. The thesis focuses on assessing the 'shift of the norm' through its chosen methodology and research questions. To illustrate potential variability in water stress, graphs of monthly and yearly data are provided, showing fluctuations beyond the presented range. However, the study does not aim to precisely model or predict extreme events or their probabilities.

Based on the research objective, the following research questions can be formulated:

1. How will climate change affect water availability and demand in the Gürbe catchment for the period 2045–2074?
2. Will there be months with chronic water stress according to the water stress index (WSI) in the Gürbe catchment between 2045–2074?
3. How will the annual WSI values develop and will there be years in the medium term where the annual WSI values exceed the "high stress" threshold?
4. What were the main water management challenges during the summer droughts of 2018 and 2022?

The first three research questions are addressed by estimating future water availability and demand. The demand is estimated on the basis of four consumption categories, while the water supply is based on modelled streamflow data. The fourth research question is analysed through interviews with regional water management stakeholders.

2 Case Study

The study area encompasses the Gürbe-catchment until the hydrological measuring station Belp, Mühlmatt (BAFU-ID 2159).

The catchment area is divided into two main parts: The upper part, where the Gürbe descends as a mountain river from the Gantrisch area, and the Gürbe valley section. The Gürbetal, forming the geographical continuation of the Stockental, runs north from the Kandertal, almost parallel to the Aare valley. It is bounded by the glacially formed hills between Amsoldingen and Längenbühl in the south and Belpberg and Längenberg in the north. The Gürbetal, about 20 kilometers long, joins the Aare valley at Belp, forming the Belpmoos floodplain.

Figure 2: Map of the Gürbe catchment. Land use data from Federal Statistical Office (2018).

The average elevation of the catchment area is 849 m asl., with an elevation range of 2128 to 508 m asl. The terrain is moderately sloping with an average slope of 12 degrees. In particular, areas with a slope of less than 3 degrees make up 0.21% of the region, while those with a slope of more than 15 degrees make up 0.3%. The catchment area covers 116.1 km (HADES, 2015).

2.1 Land use

The predominant land use is agriculture, which covers 48% of the catchment. 24% of the area is covered by forests and 19% by grass and herbaceous vegetation. 6% of the catchment area is residential (Bundesamt für Statistik BFS, 2018). Agriculture in the Gürbetal used to be mainly known for its cabbage production, but this has declined significantly since the turn of the millennium. Nowadays, the main crops grown in the region are various cereals and maize. Meadows and (summer) pastures make up the largest part of the agricultural area (Kanton Bern, 2024). 2020, there were approximately 27'000¹ units of livestock within the catchment. The most common livestock (in terms of animal numbers) are cattle, poultry and pigs, which each account for around

1. Grossvieheinheiten, vgl. (Der Schweizerische Bundesrat, 1998).

10'000 animals (Kanton Bern, 2023a). Currently, around 21'000 people reside in the catchment (Kanton Bern, 2023b). There are approximately 4'000 full-time jobs available, from which 68% are in the third sector. The share of second sector is steadily declining. 1990, the second sector made up 45% of full-time equivalents (Kanton Bern, 2022).

2.2 Geology & Hydrogeology

Geologically, the Gürbetal comprises the glacially widened trough between Belp and Burgistein, which is deepened into the Midland Molasse, and the adjacent, generally less deepened section between Wattenwil and Pohlern to the south (Soom, 1999, p. 86). The Gürbetal is separated from the Stockental by a narrowing of the valley and a rock bar in the Oberstocken area. The adjacent mountainous area is of Penninic origin and consists of the Klippendecke and the Gurnigeldecke. The northern part of the valley is bordered by molasse and moraine hills. The lithology of the valley floor consists of quaternary deposits.

2.2.1 Hydrogeology: Adjacent Hills & Mountains

The slopes on the western side of the valley are characterized by loose rock with varying permeability (moraines) and solid rock (marl, clay stone; Tripet et al., 2018). In the northern part of the catchment area, on the west side of the Gürbe, the moraine hill Längenberg is situated. There are a number of springs at the foot of Längenberg, from which most have an average flow rate of 60 to 600 l/minute (Pasquier et al., 1999). In the area of the Gurnigeldecke² (on the southwestern slope of the catchment area), the groundwater yield is low to non-existent and there are only few springs (apart from the source of the Gürbe; Pasquier et al., 1999). The southern end of the catchment area lies at the foot of the Stockhorn mountain range and is characterized by solid rocks of the Klippendecke³, some of which are capable of karstification, with low groundwater productivity. There are several springs in this area with an average discharge of more than 600 l/minute (Pasquier et al., 1999; Tripet et al., 2018). The area northeast of the valley floor is dominated by the Belpberg, whose flanks consist of molasse rocks. The groundwater occurrence there is low. Accord-

2. "Gurnigel-Nappe"

3. "Klippen-Nappe"

ingly, there are only little springs in this part of the catchment area. The southeast of the catchment area consists of the uniform moraine landscape of the Thuner Westamt and has a low groundwater yield. There are no springs in this area (HADES, 2015; Pasquier et al., 1999).

Figure 3: Groundwater Map of the Gürbe catchment. Cutout from the Hydrological Atlas of Switzerland (HADES, 2015; Tripet et al., 2018).

2.2.2 Hydrogeology: Valley Floor

There are two isolated groundwater sources in the valley floor of the Gürbe catchment. In the upper Gürbetal, between Burgistein and Wattenwil, the bedrock consists of Flysch from the Gurnigeldecke and sub-alpine Molasse rock. The bedrock surface is about 30–40 meters below the surface. South of Wattenwil, the heterogeneous Gürbe talus fan dominates. There, gravelly Gürbe deposits up to 20 m thick overlie the bedrock. At the narrowing of the Gürbe valley below Wattenwil, the aquifer forms an approximately 50m deep channel that has been eroded into the bedrock. The channel is filled with post-glacial lake clays, which are overlain by Gürbe gravels, which in turn are partly covered by sub-recent gravel channels of the Gürbe. The average groundwater discharge at Gürbmatt is 150 l/s (Soom, 1999). Below the Gürbmatt the Gürbetal widens. In the Lohnstorf-Noflen area, the trough fill consists of groundwater-bearing

Gürbeschotter up to 80 m thick, which decreases towards the north and is only 5–7 m thick at Mühleturmen. This aquifer is completely wedged to the north of Mühleturmen. The groundwater flow (approx. 190 l/s) exfiltrates completely into the Müsche (a tributary of the Gürbe) via several drainage pipes (Soom, 1999).

Down the valley, the bedrock reaches a maximum depth of 200–250 meters. The quaternary valley fill consists mainly of fine-grained, impermeable unconsolidated rock without groundwater. There is an isolated aquifer near Toffen. Here, the Gürbetal gravel rests on molasse rock that dips towards the center of the valley. Because of the long reaction time to precipitation events, this aquifer is thought to be fed by lateral inflows from the Längenberg. Hydrochemical differences in nitrite levels suggest that there is no connection between this aquifer and the aquifer above Mühleturmen (Soom, 1999).

At the end of the valley, before the Gürbe enters the Belp-basin, the groundwater circulating in the quaternary sediments accumulates in a low-permeability sill zone that fills the entire valley cross-section and exfiltrates diffusely into the Gürbe through drainage pipes (Soom, 1999).

2.3 Soils

The soils in the Gürbe valley, in accord to the diverse bedrock and topography, are not homogenous in the catchment and vary in regard of their water-carrying capacity.

The Klippendecke area is dominated by shallow and poorly developed soils with low retention capacity. In the Gurnigeldecke Flysch zone, wet soils dominate. Their retention capacity is limited. Runoff in these areas is usually rapid (IHW 1997 in Salvisberg, 2017). In the lower areas with molasse and moraine deposits, brown earths and luvisols are predominant. In terms of area, they are the main soil type in the Gürbe catchment. The steep slopes of the Längenberg and Belpberg are dominated by more shallow brown earths with lower storage capacity. In the moraine landscapes of the Thuner Westamt, drainless sinks lead to the formation of peatlands with gley soils and gleyed brown earths (Salvisberg, 2017). In general, the soils of the Längenberg, Belpberg and Westamt have a high water-holding capacity, resulting in deflected runoff. This effect is less dominant in the steep slope areas (IHW in Salvisberg, 2017).

In the valley floor of the Gürbetal, in the area of the municipalities of Mühlethurnen, Kirchthurnen and Kaufdorf, there is a total of around 350 hectares of peat soil (Guenat, 2022). In the 1920s, an old fen was drained and utilized for agricultural purposes. The peat layer, which was once 3.5 meters thick, now forms a silty, humus-rich working horizon with an average thickness of around 40 cm, having been drained and intensively used since then. Due to the peat subsidence, the productivity of the soil is already reduced today (Kanton Bern, 2017). The subsidence rate in the Gürbetal is around 1 meter per 100 years. After heavy rainfall, the inadequate and outdated drainage systems create extensive surface water, making use of the land even more difficult. Due to the progressive subsidence of the peat soil, the intensity of cultivation will have to be reduced in the future, particularly in the deep peat soils with shallow silt horizons in the center of the valley. More shallow peat areas with thicker silt layers from adjacent hills (> 40cm) at the edge of the valley plain will continue to be used as arable crop land (Kanton Bern, 2017). The addition of extra mineral material in order to maintain the production capacity of the peat soils is made impossible by the prevalent subsoil, consisting of poorly consolidated lake sediments, as there is a risk of sagging (Kanton Bern, 2017). The drainage systems of the peat soils are connected to the Gürbe or its tributaries.

2.4 Ecosystem

The fluvial ecosystem of the Gürbe is known for various (fish) species, in particular for the presence of brown trout, bullheads and crayfish. However, due to recent summer heat waves, a change is now becoming apparent. Summers are becoming too hot for brown trout and other established species, which has already led to several mass mortalities. The increasingly irregular flow regime, with more frequent peak flows in late autumn due to reduced snowfall, is also hampering the spawning of traditional Gürbe fish species. It is possible for fish to migrate from the Aare into the Gürbe. As a result, the Gürbe is increasingly inhabited by white fish species, which are better able to cope with the high temperatures. There are also beavers in the Müsche (Gürbe tributary; Fischereiinspektorat Kanton Bern, 2024).

3 Data

3.1 Climate Data

3.1.1 Observed Data: Gridded Data Products

MeteoSwiss provides daily gridded datasets for various climatological variables covering the time range from 1961 to the present (SrelD: 1971–present). These analyses are derived from a combination of weather station data, satellite imagery, radar and topographic information to estimate climate conditions at locations without direct measurements. The datasets are updated daily and can be used for both real-time monitoring and long-term climate analysis.

The RhiresD dataset provided by MeteoSwiss (2021a) provides spatially interpolated daily precipitation totals for Switzerland. The data is derived from rain gauge measurements at over 400 stations in Switzerland and neighbouring regions. RhiresD has its uncertainties, particularly in mountainous areas and for extreme precipitation events. These uncertainties arise from factors such as wind-induced undercatch at rain gauges and the challenges of interpolating precipitation over complex terrain.

The TabsD datasets from MeteoSwiss (2021b) provides daily gridded analysis of the mean air temperatures at 2 meters above ground level across Switzerland. The dataset is derived from a network of approximately 90 long-term homogenized station records. The temperature interpolation method accounts for vertical temperature profiles and non-Euclidean distances to enhance accuracy, particularly in mountainous areas. Despite careful homogenization, interpolation errors—especially in winter and in regions with complex terrain—remain, with mean absolute errors ranging from 0.6°C on the Swiss Plateau to up to 1.6°C in the Alps.

The SrelD dataset from (MeteoSwiss, 2021c) provides daily spatial analyses of relative sunshine duration across Switzerland, expressed as a percentage of maximum potential sunshine (1971–present). The dataset integrates approximately 70 ground-based measurements with high-resolution satellite-derived clearness indices. The methodology, combining station and satellite data via a Principal Component Analysis (PCA), enhances spatial resolution and accuracy, especially in distinguishing cloud patterns over complex terrain. Validation shows median errors of 7–10% relative sunshine duration, with reduced accuracy in regions of complex cloud structures.

3.1.2 Modelled Data: CH2018 Climate Data

To project future climatological developments within our catchment, data from the CH2018 climate change modeling project (see Fischer et al., 2022; NCCS, 2018) was used. All information presented below is summarized from the technical report of the project (see NCCS, 2018).

The BAFU CH2018 project, also known as CH2018 (from here on referred as such), is a Swiss climate change study organized by the Federal Office for the Environment (BAFU) of Switzerland. It focuses on assessing the future climate of Switzerland based on different scenarios of greenhouse gas emissions.

The CH2018 framework provides climate projections for Switzerland based on simulations from the EURO-CORDEX⁴ ensemble. The scenarios include the three Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs), presented in section 4.1 (RCP 2.6; 4.5; 8.5). The projections focus on future seasonal changes in both mean climatological parameters (temperature, precipitation etc.) and extreme events. Historical data from MeteoSwiss provides a baseline to extrapolate and compare future changes.

CH2018 relies on Regional Climate Models (RCMs) to refine global climate data from General Circulation Models (GCMs). These models help resolve Europe's complex topography and project regionalized climate changes. The climate projections are derived from EURO-CORDEX simulations, which operate on grid resolutions of 12 and 50 km. These simulations are driven by RCPs that reflect different future emission pathways.

The CH2018 future projections are divided into three periods: 2020–2049, 2045–2074, and 2070–2099, centered on the years 2035, 2060, and 2085, respectively. These future periods are consistent with previous Swiss climate scenarios and international climate assessments.

Switzerland is divided into five model regions in the CH2018 project to better capture local climate variability and ensure more accurate projections. This regional division enables more detailed analysis of climate impacts in different parts of the country. To further improve the spatial resolution of the climate projections, CH2018 employs quantile mapping as a statistical downscaling technique. This method adjusts the model outputs to match observed local conditions by aligning the distribution of simulated data with that of historical observations. While RCMs provide data at a 12 or a

4. EURO-CORDEX (European Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment) is a scientific initiative that provides high-resolution climate projections for Europe. It was established by the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) to improve regional climate predictions.

50 km grid scale, quantile mapping corrects for model biases and generates higher-resolution data suitable for local impact assessments. The downscaling process is crucial for applications requiring precise climate information. However, the method carries uncertainties, particularly in relation to extreme events.

In the CH2018 publications, the uncertainty is assessed through a multi-model ensemble approach, using a 90% quantile range to capture the variability in projections. This range reflects uncertainties stemming from model imperfections, internal climate variability, and future emissions scenarios. However, the ensemble is not comprehensive and is considered an "ensemble of opportunity," meaning it may not fully represent the full scope of climate model uncertainties and its model choice mainly was based on the available GCM-RCM model chains.

Two statistically downscaled data products are available. They cover daily data from 1981 to 2099.

- **DAILY-LOCAL:** Includes data for the individual MeteoSwiss weather stations, including the variables temperature (daily mean, maximum, and minimum), precipitation, relative humidity, global radiation, and near-surface wind speed.
- **DAILY-GRIDDED:** Provides a nationwide 2-km grid that including the variables daily mean, maximum, and minimum temperature and precipitation.

For the gridded variables, as well as the local variable near-surface wind speed and global radiation, 68 model chains are available. 12 are RCP 2.6 model chains, 25 RCP 4.5 and 31 RCP 8.5. 20 pairs of data timeseries stem from the same model chain with a different spatial resolution (ordered by ascending RCP scenario: 3, 8, 9). For the variable relative humidity, 47 different model chain timeseries are available (Nr. of pairs only differing in resolution indicated in brackets: RCP 2.6: 8 (1); RCP 4.5: 17 (5); RCP 8.5: 22 (5)).

For the calculation of the potential crop evapotranspiration (see section [4.5.2](#)), the variables temperature (daily mean, minimum, maximum), surface downward solar radiation (rsds), relative humidity (hurs), and wind speed were needed. To receive the irrigation demand, precipitation projections were further considered.

3.2 Hydrological Data

3.2.1 Observed Data

The observed streamflow data for the Gürbe are from the hydrological measuring station "Belp-Mühlimatt", located at the entrance of the Gürbe into the Belpmoos plain. Due to the local geology (see section 2.2), there is no unmeasured subterranean groundwater flow below the station. The station has been in operation since 1923 and has been providing daily streamflow measurements ever since. The station is located at 522 m asl. The station does not have a low water channel.

Figure 4: Hydrological measuring station Belp-Mühlimatt (Photo: Bundesamt für Umwelt).

3.2.2 Modelled Data

In the Hydro-CH18 project, the climate data resulting from the CH2018-project (see section above) was used to run the hydrological model PREVAH in a total of 93 catchments across Switzerland for the period 1981–2099 (Muelchi et al., 2022a). The simulations are designed to analyze the impacts of climate change on runoff under the three RCP-scenarios. The model datasets consists of streamflow data generated by 67 dif-

ferent model chains. The RCP 8.5 model chains are the most frequent with 30, for the RCP 4.5 scenario, 25 model chains were available and 12 for the RCP 2.6 scenario. 20 pairs of simulated streamflow timeseries are of the same model chain with a different resolution (RCP 2.6: 3; RCP 4.5: 8; RCP 8.5: 9).

The PREVAH hydrological modeling system (Viviroli et al., 2007) is designed for simulating water-related processes in catchments with complex topography, particularly in mountainous regions. It uses a semi-distributed approach by dividing catchments into Hydrological Response Units (HRUs), which allows it to capture spatial and temporal variability in processes such as evapotranspiration, snowmelt, glacier melt, runoff generation, and flood routing. The system incorporates tools for preprocessing, calibration, and post-processing, and requires meteorological and physio-graphical data like temperature, precipitation, soil, and elevation.

Figure 5: Model setup Hydro CH2018 (Muelchi et al., 2022).

In the Hydro-CH2018 project, the model was calibrated using the even years of the observed data from 1985 to 2014 and validated using the uneven years within the same period. To validate the model, several metrics, including the Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) and Kling-Gupta Efficiency (KGE) were applied. The choice to use the uneven years to assess the model performance was made, since many extreme years were of an uneven number (i.e. 2003) and thus the model performance during extreme events could be assessed. Land use was assumed to remain constant, only glacier extent was constantly adjusted.

NSE values range from the lowest values of 0.7 to highest values of 0.91. The median KGE value across all catchments is 0.89 in both periods, and ranges between 0.71 and 0.93 in the calibration period and 0.75 and 0.96 in the validation period (Muelchi et al., 2022b, p. 53).

Figure 6: Model performance across all 93 modeled catchments (Muelchi et al., 2022).

The modelled streamflow data is subject to several uncertainties. First, there is the assumption of stationary model biases due to the downscaling of input data using quantile mapping. Second, the calibrated model parameters are assumed to remain stationary, even under climate change. Third, land use is presumed to remain unchanged, with the exception of glacial cover. Finally, the reliance on a single hydrological model introduces uncertainty, as different models can produce significantly different streamflow magnitudes, particularly in highly glaciated catchments.

The performance statistic for the Gürbe catchment reveals a good performance across all performance metrics that lies within the average range for all simulated catchments.

Table 2: Performance statistics for the Gürbe-Mühlimatt catchment (ID 2159).

NSE_{cal}	NSE_{val}	$NSE_{sqrt\ cal}$	$NSE_{sqrt\ val}$	KGE_{cal}	KGE_{val}
0.8	0.82	0.82	0.85	0.89	0.87

3.3 Agricultural & Demographic Data

To estimate current and future water demand, further data sources, encompassing agricultural and demographic subjects, were considered. They are briefly described below.

Land use data for the catchment area were obtained from the Swiss "Arealstatistik 2018" of the Swiss Federal Statistical Office. The land use raster has a resolution of 100x100m and provides different levels of land use classifications. For my analysis, I chose the basic land use classification, which has four categories: residential, agricultural, timbered / forest and unproductive. The data was collected through a combination of field work and aerial image analysis and is publicly available (Bundesamt für Statistik BFS, 2018).

The shapefile depicting the extent of the peat soils in the Gürbetal was obtained from the Bernese Cantonal Office for Agriculture and Nature (LANAT). The file is not publicly available and was sent to me after reaching out to the office. I do not know the method of the data collection.

The dataset on agricultural land use patterns includes the geographical locations of crops, recorded by contribution year. For this analysis, the data reflects the status of agricultural crop areas in 2023. Data is collected by the responsible authorities of the Canton of Bern as part of the agricultural subsidy system. The data is publicly accessible (Kanton Bern, 2024). The number of livestock per municipality, broken down by type of livestock, is recorded as part of the agricultural structure survey of the Federal Statistical Office. The publicly available data cover the years 1975–2020, with data always available at 5-year intervals. The survey is carried out as part of the coordination of administrative data under the Direct Payments Ordinance (Bundesamt für Statistik, 2024).

The number of residents per municipality was obtained from two data sources: For the years 1990 and 2000, the values were obtained from a dataset provided by the Canton of Bern, which contains values for Bernese municipalities from the 2000 Federal Population Census. More recent values were provided from the Statistical Office of the Canton of Bern, in a dataset containing the number of residents for all Bernese municipalities for the years 2010–2022 (Kanton Bern, 2023b). Both datasets are publicly available online.

Future number of residents were obtained from the "Scenarios for population development" in Switzerland, provided by the Swiss Federal Statistical Office. The projections encompass different scenarios. In this study, the "Mittel" scenario data was used. The "Mittel" scenario projects Switzerland's population to grow from 8.69 million in 2020 to 10.44 million by 2050, with slower growth over time and a decreasing proportion of the working-age population (Bundesamt für Statistik BFS, 2020). The granularity of the federal data is canton-wide, the revised publication of the data by the Canton of Bern also incorporates growth by cantonal area types (Kanton Bern, 2021).

Cantonal 2nd and 3rd sector full-time equivalent (FTE) data for the 1985–2001 period were provided by the institute for Historical statistics of Switzerland (Historische Statistik der Schweiz, 2012). This dataset is not publicly available and had to be requested via E-Mail. The period thereafter (2000–2020) was included in the dataset “STATENT 2021” from the Federal Statistical Office, which covers the development of FTE’s in Swiss municipalities (Bundesamt für Statistik BFS, 2021).

4 Methods

4.1 Key Concepts

4.1.1 Drought Processes

Drought is broadly described as a prolonged and widespread period of below-average water availability in a given region. It represents a significant reduction in the water that ecosystems and human societies have historically relied on. Drought is a relative concept, reflecting abnormal conditions in environmental factors such as precipitation, soil moisture, groundwater levels, and streamflow. The impact of drought is most acute during the low flow season (Tallaksen and Van Lanen, 2024).

The root cause of drought is typically an extended period of insufficient rainfall, known as meteorological drought. This initial shortfall in precipitation sets off a chain reaction throughout the hydrological cycle, leading to various forms of drought. When high evaporation rates accompany the lack of rain, soil moisture levels can drop significantly, resulting in soil moisture drought, which adversely affects vegetation and agriculture (also called agricultural drought). Over time, reduced groundwater recharge and streamflow lead to hydrological drought, characterized by a deficit in available water resources. The time lag between the onset of meteorological drought and hydrological drought can vary widely, from days in areas with rapid runoff to months or years in regions reliant on groundwater (Tallaksen and Van Lanen, 2024).

Further classifications encompass the ecological drought, a state in which water shortages put stress on ecosystems, negatively impacting plant and animal life. The term socio-economic drought focuses on the broader consequences of drought on society and the economy, as well as the strategies used to manage these impacts (Tallaksen and Van Lanen, 2024).

4.1.2 Drought Hazard

Recognising drought as a hazard requires an understanding of vulnerability and risk, where disaster risk is defined by the probability of the event occurring and the potential severity of its impacts, such as financial losses and ecological damage. Drought is particularly threatening in arid regions, especially in developing countries, where it often leads to crop failure, mass livestock deaths and subsequent hunger. In wealthier areas, such as the US and Europe, the effects are felt mainly on an environmental and economic level. Unlike other natural disasters, drought develops gradually and can go unnoticed for a long time. The earliest signs are usually seen in plant growth, as the limited water reserves in the soil are rapidly depleted during warm, dry weather. This depletion stresses both natural drought-sensitive plants and agricultural crops, leading to potential losses in wildlife habitat and agricultural production. If drought persists, it can cause natural vegetation and riparian areas to dry out, affecting wildlife, while groundwater recharge declines, streamflow decreases, and water levels in lakes and aquifers drop, posing significant challenges to water resources. The economic impact of drought is greatest in regions with large populations and extensive industrial development, while human suffering is greatest in less developed countries (Tallaksen and Van Lanen, 2024).

4.1.3 Water Stress

Fjörke and Alcamo (2004), referring to various literature sources, define water stress as “a measure of the amount of pressure put on water resources and aquatic ecosystems by the users of these resources”. Users include, amongst others, municipalities, industries, power stations and agricultural users. Wada et al. (2011, p. 1) point out that with rising water stress, the population of a region “will be more vulnerable (...) to water scarcity”. They furthermore specify water stress as the pressure put on blue water resources. Wada et al. (2011, p. 3) characterize water stress as a state that occurs, “when different types of water demand compete for the same scarce water resources”.

4.1.4 RCP-Scenarios

The Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) are a set of four⁵ scenarios developed by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) to model potential future climate conditions based on varying levels of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. These scenarios enable an understanding of the potential impacts of climate change and the effectiveness of mitigation efforts.

RCP 2.6: This is the most optimistic scenario, aiming to keep global temperature rise below 2°C by 2100. It requires significant and immediate reductions in GHG emissions, with CO₂ emissions peaking around 2020 and then declining rapidly. This scenario assumes widespread adoption of renewable energy and other low-carbon technologies, achieving net-negative emissions by the latter half of the century.

RCP 4.5: This scenario represents moderate mitigation efforts, where emissions peak around 2040 and then decline. It assumes the implementation of climate policies that limit radiative forcing to 4.5 W/m² by 2100. Although less ambitious than RCP2.6, it still requires substantial changes in energy production and consumption patterns, including a significant reduction in the use of fossil fuels.

RCP 8.5: Known as the "business as usual" or worst-case scenario, RCP8.5 assumes continued high emissions throughout the century, with little to no efforts to decrease GHG emissions. This scenario would result in a radiative forcing of 8.5 W/m² by 2100, leading to a significant global temperature rise of over 4°C. It predicts severe climate impacts, including more frequent extreme weather events, substantial sea-level rise, and widespread disruption to ecosystems and human societies.

Each of these RCPs illustrates the potential outcomes based on different levels of climate action, highlighting the critical importance of mitigation efforts in shaping our future climate (IPCC, 2008; Van Vuuren et al., 2011).

4.2 Data Analysis

To provide an overview of the climatological characteristics of the catchments, time-series plots of the climatic variables temperature, precipitation and relative sunshine duration were included. The plots, based on gridded MeteoSwiss data (see section 3.1.1), cover the years 1960–2021 (temperature and precipitation) and 1971–2021 (relative sunshine duration). Furthermore, a monthly climate diagram covering the period 1992–2021 is included.

5. The RCP 6.0 scenario is not considered further as it is not included in the BAFU2018 data.

Figure 7: The four RCP-Scenarios (Figure from Van Vuuren et al., 2011).

For the data analysis of the existing hydrological records, observed streamflow data were analysed. For all hydrological analyses, the most recent 30-year period for which all required data were available was selected (see chapter 3). The analysis included the creation of a plot showing the seasonal patterns of streamflow through monthly box plots. A flow duration curve was furthermore added. The flow duration curve was constructed by ranking the daily flow values and plotting them against their exceedance probability. The NM7Q measures the lowest average streamflow over seven days in a year (NCCS, 2021). A timeseries plot showing the annual NM7Q values for the years 1974–2023 was included. This longer period was chosen to show a larger time series.

An estimate of the seasonal evapotranspiration cycle was made by subtracting the average monthly streamflow values from the average monthly precipitation values following Bormann et al. (2016). Annual evapotranspiration was estimated using the same method.

The brief analysis of Gürbes baseflow trends is presented in two graphs: One showing the average monthly baseflow index and one showing a time series of summer monthly baseflow indices from 1979 to 2021. This longer period was chosen to show a larger time series.

Baseflow separation is a key technique for distinguishing groundwater contributions (baseflow) from total streamflow in a hydrological system. The method of Duncan (2019) applied here applies a combination of graphical approaches and automated algorithms, extracting baseflow by applying recession analysis to identify the groundwater contribution during non-storm periods. This method integrates hydrograph separation techniques with recession curve analysis to ensure a clear division between fast and slow components of streamflow. The baseflow index describes the proportion of baseflow in the total streamflow (Singh et al., 2019).

4.3 Interviews

As part of this study, a total of five people were interviewed who each deal with one or two categories of water use in their everyday lives. The aim was to embed the results of the quantitative evaluations in the local context. The focus was particularly on getting to know the challenges in water management in the past heatwave summers of 2018 and 2022. In addition, the interviews with local water stakeholders were intended to ensure that local knowledge could be incorporated into the theoretical work.

4.3.1 Data Collection

The interviews were semi-structured, i.e. the questions were asked using a predefined questionnaire. The questions were sent to the interviewees in advance. The interviews were recorded or notes were made continuously. The interviews lasted between 30 and 80 minutes. The two representatives of the Wasserbauverband were interviewed together. The representative of the Office for Waste and Water of the Canton of Berne answered my questions in writing and in an additional telephone call as he was unable to attend the interview due to unforeseen circumstances.

The following persons were interviewed (organization & occupation):

- Wasserbauverband Untere Gürbe⁶ und Müsche, Vice-president; Farmer
- Wasserbauverband Untere Gürbe und Müsche, long time former president; catchment resident
- Cantonal Fisheries Inspectorate, Head of Fisheries Management
- Cantonal Office for Water and Waste (AWA), Water supply specialist
- Blattenheid Drinking Water Supply, Head of Service

6. "Water construction association lower Gürbe"

4.3.2 Data Analysis

As the interviews were conducted to obtain additional information, a targeted thematic analysis was carried out. This allowed relevant information and patterns to be extracted from the transcripts without the need for an exhaustive, line-by-line coding process. The transcripts/notes were reviewed in detail to gain an understanding of the key points raised by the participants. Relevant findings in relation to the overarching research theme were recorded in notes.

The main themes were then identified, and the findings sorted accordingly. The identification of the main topics was based, among other things, on the main categories of water use, which are dealt with in greater depth in the quantitative analysis. The focus was on information that improved the understanding of the quantitative evaluation, such as local irrigation practices and the local effects of insufficient residual flows.

The relevant topics were summarized, paying particular attention to the extent to which they could complement or challenge the results of the quantitative part.

4.4 Assessment of Water Stress

4.4.1 Time Periods

The assessment of water stress was conducted using different methodological approaches. Generally, the goal was to reveal monthly and yearly developments in water usage and availability. To better structure the results, three periods of interest were defined:

- 1990–2019: present, observed period
- 2020–2049: short-term
- 2045–2074: medium-term

These periods align with the ones used in the CH2018 project (see section [3.1.2](#)). For each period, all water stress evaluation-metrics were calculated for each RCP-period.

4.4.2 Water Stress Index

The primary index used to assess water stress is the water stress index that describes the proportion between the monthly water needs and the available water resources within the catchment. The index illustrates the anthropogenic pressure applied to water resources. The index, first described by Shiklomanov in 1993, is known under various names: Brown (2011) includes the index in his overview of water scarcity indices as “water resource vulnerability index”, Alcamo et al. (2000) describe the same index as the “criticality ratio”. In this master thesis, the index is from here on referred to as the water stress index (WSI), as in Milano et al. (2016).

$$WSI = \frac{D}{A} \quad (1)$$

D = Demand, A = Availability

A state of high water stress occurs if the long-term, annual average of the water stress index exceeds 0.4 (Alcamo et al., 2000; Kundzewicz et al., 2007; Raskin, 1997). For my monthly analysis, I will apply the same threshold for a high water stress state. I will use the same water stress levels as Milano et al. (2016).

Table 3: Levels of water stress, analog to Milano et al. (2016).

Range	Label
≤ 0.1	No Stress
0.1 – 0.2	Low Stress
0.2 – 0.4	Moderate Stress
0.4 – 0.8	High Stress
≥ 0.8	Severe Stress

To assess the (future) water stress in our catchment, the index was calculated on a monthly and on an annual basis for each 30-year period. The data was aggregated using median-values. To illustrate uncertainties, the quantiles $Q_{0.85}$ and $Q_{0.15}$ were used.

4.4.3 Data Aggregation

For demand calculations including modelled data⁷, each resulting variable was calculated for every model separately and then aggregated. To aggregate the data, monthly median-values as well as the $Q_{0.15}$ and $Q_{0.85}$ values were calculated for every period across all model chains. The same was done to obtain annual values. This was done for each RCP-scenario.

To get an impression of possible future extreme events, the results section contains tables and graphs depicting the distribution of the water stress levels of individual months and years across all model chains (without aggregating the data to a 30-year median).

4.5 Water Demand Estimations & Availability

4.5.1 Water Availability

To assess the water resource availability, streamflow data from Muelchi et al. (2022a) were used (see section 3.2.2). The data was aggregated by the method described in section 4.4.3.

4.5.2 Irrigation: Crop Coefficient Approach

The irrigation water need was determined as the difference between the rolling mean of the precipitation over the last seven days and the specific crop water requirement. This calculation was performed separately for each climate model. For each 30-year period and RCP-scenario, the irrigation demand is calculated according to the aggregation method described in section 4.4.3. The cropping patterns were assumed to remain consistent.

The crop water need was calculated through the crop coefficient approach by Allen et al. (1998). This method estimates crop evapotranspiration (ET_c), a proxy for the crop-specific water need. The crop coefficient approach involves three main steps:

First, the reference evapotranspiration (ET_0) is determined. ET_0 represents the rate of evapotranspiration from a reference surface, a well-watered grass field. This is calculated using the Penman-Monteith equation, which incorporates the climatic parameters temperature, humidity, wind speed, and solar radiation.

7. Irrigation (evapotranspiration and precipitation)

Next, a crop coefficient (K_c) specific to the crop and its growth stage is applied to the ET_0 . The K_c values account for the differences between the reference crop and the actual crop's evapotranspiration characteristics. K_c values vary throughout the crop's development stages: initial, mid-season, and late season.

Figure 8: K_c -curve, divided into the four growth-stages (Allen et al., 1998, p. 100)

With the K_c , crop-specific changes on the evapotranspiration are considered. The K_c represents the changes caused by the crop height, the top soil surface Albedo, the canopy resistance and the evapotranspiration from the soil. The K_c -values are also influenced by local climatic variables and should therefore be adjusted if necessary. The initial K_c values are “are subject to the effects of large variations in wetting frequencies” (Allen et al., 1998, p. 109) and should therefore be adjusted according to the frequency and the magnitude of wetting events. Lower wind speeds and more humid climates lead to lower $K_{c\ mid}$ values (Allen et al., 1998, p. 124). The adjustments hence depend on these two variables. $K_{c\ end}$ value adjustments mainly depend on the water management strategy for the crop type (harvested fresh or dried out). However, the values are also reduced by higher humidity and lower wind speeds, if the RH_{\min} differs from 45% or u_2 is larger or smaller than 2.0 m/s (Allen et al., 1998, p. 125).

The crop coefficient approach divides the growth process into four stages. The initial stage spans from planting until about 10% of the ground is covered by the crop. This is followed by the crop development stage, which extends from 10% ground cover to the beginning of full coverage. The mid-season stage corresponds to the period of full ground cover, marking the peak water use of the crop. Finally, the late season stage begins after the mid-season stage and lasts until harvest, during which the crop's water use gradually declines.

After the construction of the K_c -curve, according to the obtained data specifying the regional length of the growth stages, the Crop Evapotranspiration can be determined:

$$ET_c = K_c \cdot ET_0 \quad (2)$$

ET_c = crop evapotranspiration [$mm\ d^{-1}$]

K_c = crop coefficient [dimensionless]

ET_0 = reference crop evapotranspiration [$mm\ d^{-1}$]

For this thesis, the reference evapotranspiration (ET_0) within the catchment was calculated using the Penman-Monteith equation as recommended by Allen et al. (1998). The input data was taken from the CH2018 project (see section 3.1.2).

The daily ET_0 was separately calculated for every climate model (a total of 47 models). Since only the temperature data was available as a gridded product, the other needed variables (relative humidity, wind speed and solar radiation downward shortwave) were taken from the Zollikofen weather station, for which said variables were available. The temperature was taken as the mean catchment value from the DAILY-GRIDDED dataset.

The crop coefficient values (K_c) were collected for the 15 most frequent crops in the year 2023 within the catchment (Not including cereals, meadows and grasslands). For the K_c -values, the values from Table 11 in the FAO report Nr. 56 were used (Allen et al., 1998, p. 104). The length of the growing periods as well as the planting date was adjusted using various sources, mainly Swiss agricultural consultative documents. A full list of crops, including crop coefficients, can be found in the supplementary material (see Appendix A).

The $K_{c\ ini}$ values were adjusted using the formula Nr. 59 from Allen et al. (1998, p. 117), as the average wetting depth of a precipitation event within the catchment is between 22 and 36mm (depending on the season). The $K_{c\ mid}$ values were not adjusted, since no data for the mean daily minimum relative humidity was available.

The adjustment would most likely only have caused minor changes, since the average wind speed is close to 2m/s, which leads to no change in the $K_{c\ mid}$ values for sub-humid climates (see Allen et al., 1998, p. 122). The $K_{c\ end}$ values were not adjusted, also because no data for the mean daily minimum relative humidity were available.

To obtain the mean ET_c values for the whole agricultural cropping area (as an estimate of agricultural crop water demand), daily weighted K_c values were calculated, considering the cropping area of the different crops. Crops outside their growing season for the specific day of the year were not considered. Cereals, meadows, and pastures were not considered. The decision not to consider cereal cropland as irrigated was made because current agricultural price policies make irrigation of cereals uneconomical, which is therefore not practiced.

Figure 9: The average crop coefficient for the Gürbe catchment, based on the cropping patterns for the year 2023.

To receive the irrigation demand, the difference between the theoretical crop water demand (ET_c) and the average precipitation of the last seven days was calculated. The precipitation data, as well as the other input data for the evapotranspiration calculation, were obtained from project CH2018.

4.5.3 Livestock Water Need

Livestock water need was computed by multiplying the daily water need per unit by the livestock numbers provided by the Swiss Federal Statistical Office (Bundesamt für Statistik, 2024). One unit of livestock needs 110l water per day (Freiburghaus, 2009). It was assumed that the demand for water by livestock would remain constant over the course of the year and would not be influenced by the different RCP scenarios.

To obtain the number of livestock, all municipalities within the catchment area were considered and the number of livestock was then adjusted according to the percentage of agricultural area within the catchment⁸. The values were then extrapolated to the year 2080, taking into account current agricultural trends. For each livestock category,

8. According to the Swiss Area Statistic 2018 (categorization: 4 main categories of "NOAS04"; Bundesamt für Statistik BFS, 2018).

future projections were approached using three methods: linear extrapolation of past trends, maintaining the 2020 values as constants, or using the average values from the entire observation period (1975–2020). For animal categories with a clear trend in the observed numbers, which were not in contradiction with the literature (Blair et al., 2024; European Commission, 2020b), the future values were extrapolated linearly until 2050 and then assumed to remain constant (cattle, sheep, goats). In instances where the observed trend did not align with the findings documented in the literature, the livestock categories in question were assumed to remain constant at either the value recorded in 2020 (equine and pigs) or at the average value over the entire observed period (poultry and other animals).

To convert the numbers of animal heads to livestock units, the conversion factors according to the Swiss Agricultural Terminology Ordinance were applied (Der Schweizerische Bundesrat, 1998).

Table 4: Conversion factor for all categories of livestock.

Animal	Livestock Unit Conversion Factor
Poultry	0.01
Equine	0.5
Cattle	0.8
Sheep	0.2
Pigs	0.3
Goats	0.2
Other Animals	0.2

4.5.4 Drinking Water Need

Drinking water need was computed by multiplying the daily water need per person by the number of habitants in the catchment. One person needs 142l water per day (including all household needs; Freiburghaus, 2015). This demand was assumed to remain constant over the course of a year. Also for all three RCP scenarios, similar developments in water demand were assumed.

To receive the numbers of catchment residents (1980–2020), the cantonal population statistics were retrieved for all the municipalities within the catchment (Kanton Bern, 2023b). The figures were then adjusted according to the percentage of the settlement area of each municipality within the catchment boundaries⁹. The evolution of the number of residents was projected using the cantonal population scenarios, which go up to the year 2050 (Kanton Bern, 2021). I used the numbers of the growth scenario “medium”. The granularity of the data was limited to the cantonal area types (“Raumtypen”) of the cantonal spatial development concept. Thus, a weighted average of the population projections was employed, according to the distribution of area types within the catchment area. For the years 2050–2080, the cantonal population projections were linearly extrapolated.

4.5.5 Industry Water Need

The industrial water demand was calculated by estimating the future number of Full Time Equivalents (FTE) in the catchment for the 2nd and 3rd sectors and then applying the water demand accordingly. One FTE in the second sector has an annual water demand of 148 m³, while one FTE in the third sector has an annual water demand of 85 m³ (Freiburghaus, 2009). The observed number of FTE’s in the Gürbetal municipalities (Bundesamt für Statistik BFS, 2021; Historische Statistik der Schweiz, 2012) were adjusted according to the percentage of the settlement area of each municipality within the catchment boundaries¹⁰. For these variables, there were no publicly available projections.

The projection of future FTE numbers was carried out using the method applied in the Canton of Berne's overall transport model (see Vrtic et al., 2023). This model assumes a 5.4% growth in total cantonal FTEs by 2040. The regional distribution of this growth is determined by two factors: the regional share of employment growth between 2011 and 2019, and the share of population growth between 2019 and 2040, with both factors weighted equally. Vrtic et al. (2023) chose this method based on the assumption that recent trends in employee number development will continue into the future. Furthermore, they assumed that an increase of the regional population will lead to the creation of new jobs. Cantonal and national planning strategies aim for people to work in the same region where they live (Vrtic et al., 2023). To determine, in which sector

9. According to the Swiss Area Statistic 2018 (categorization: 4 main categories of "NOAS04"; Bundesamt für Statistik BFS, 2018).

10. According to the Swiss Area Statistic 2018 (categorization: 4 main categories of "NOAS04"; Bundesamt für Statistik BFS, 2018).

(2nd or 3rd) the growth will occur, the shares of the sectors were identified for the observed period and this trend was assumed to continue linearly. The values for the period 2040–2075 were then extrapolated linearly on the basis of the figures obtained using the described methodology.

4.5.6 Ecology Water Need

The ecological water requirement was determined on the basis of the Swiss Water Protection Act¹¹. This basically stipulates the permanent water supply of the flow that is exceeded on 347 days per year (Q_{347}). Depending on the magnitude of this value, the residual flow is adjusted in accordance with the residual flows defined in Art. 31. For the magnitude of the Gürbe's streamflow, the rule is that the residual flow must be 130 l/s, since the calculated residual flow Q_{347} is less than 500 l/s. For every 10 l/s by which the calculated residual flow Q_{347} exceeds 160 l/s, the prescribed residual flow is increased by 4.4 l/s. This calculation was performed for all periods and RCP scenarios.

4.5.7 Types of Water Demand

To enable more differentiated results, three different types of water use were defined:

- Total water use: Including all water use categories (drinking, irrigation, livestock, industrial, ecology)
- Water use without ecology: All water use excluding ecology, since in this category, no water is “used”, but only required to be left in the channel.
- Surface water: Ecology and irrigation water, the only two water use categories that rely mainly on surface water.

11. Bundesgesetz vom 24. Januar 1991 über den Schutz der Gewässer (Gewässerschutzgesetz, GSchG).

5 Results

5.1 Catchment Climate & Hydrology

5.1.1 Climate

The average temperature in the Gürbe catchment area is 8.2°C (1992–2021). The average annual rainfall is 1238 mm, with the highest rainfall occurring in the summer months.

Figure 10: Climate diagramm for the Gürbe catchment.

Like the rest of Switzerland, the Gürbetal has experienced significant warming. During the period 1960–1990, the average temperature was 6.9°C. The 20-year running mean shows a strongly increasing trend. For the period 1992–2021, the average temperature was 8.2°C. The evolution of annual precipitation does not show a clear pattern. The mean annual precipitation sums of the 1960–1990 and 1992–2021 periods differ by only 4 mm (1242 mm and 1238 mm). The recorded time series of seasonal precipitation sums (not shown) also reveal no clear trend. Similar to temperatures, the mean relative sunshine duration shows an increasing trend. While during the period 1971–1990, 37% of the total daylight hours were sunny, this value increased to 42% for the period 1992–2021 (see [Figure 11](#)).

Figure 11: Evolution of mean annual temperature, precipitation sums and relative sunshine duration in the Gürbe catchment compared to the 1960-1990 average (relative sunshine duration: 1971–1990).

5.1.2 Hydrology

The mean streamflow of the Gürbe at Belp, Mühlimatt is $2.6 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. The flow regime, according to the classification by Aschwanden and Weingartner (1985), is pluvial supérieur. The month with the highest average streamflow is May, followed by June. The regime of the Gürbe is very unstable. The explained variance of streamflow by the Pardé coefficients is 0.11.

Although the Gürbe falls under a pluvial regime type, the streamflow is influenced by snowfall, due to the altitude of the catchment. This is represented by snow-water equivalent (SWE). The SWE corresponds to the amount of water that is produced, when an existing snow cover is completely melted. For the standard period 1981–2010, the SWE in the Gürbe catchment was 32mm in February, 40mm in March, 28mm in April and 16mm in April (always on the 1st of the month; HADES, 2015). The estimated annual evapotranspiration is 515mm (see [Figure 13](#)).

Figure 12: The monthly flow regime of the Gürbe (left) and the flow duration curve (right; 1994–2023), measured at Belp Mühlmatte.

Figure 13: Monthly precipitation and streamflow sums (in mm) and the resulting approximation of the monthly evapotranspiration.

The baseflow index of the Gürbe is 0.6, calculated as the ratio of total baseflow to total streamflow. During the winter and spring months, the index value is 0.59 and 0.57, respectively. It reaches its highest point during the summer period at 0.64. In the autumn, the index value is 0.6. There is no distinct trend evident in the timeseries of annual baseflow indexes. A similar observation can be made for three of the four seasons. Only during summer, the timeseries of the seasonal baseflow index values reveals a declining trend (see Figure 14).

The analysis of the low flow characteristics of the Gürbe reveals that the NM7Q occurs mainly during fall and winter, with a recent increase in of annual low flow values that were recorded during summer. Since 1974, the NM7Q only was recorded twice during spring time. The 15-year running mean reveals a declining trend of the NM7Q values,

Figure 14: Monthly baseflow index for the 1994–2023 period (left) and the evolution of the summer baseflow index during the 1979–2023 period (right) at Belp Mühlmatte.

with the five lowest values since 1974 all being recorded from 2010 onwards (except for 1976). These values were all measured during summer. The NMQ7 values vary significantly from year to year (mean = 0.81; standard deviation = 0.26). The Belp-Mühlmatte measuring station, where the streamflow data is measured, has no low water canal.

Figure 15: NM7Q values for the 1974–2023 period, measured at Belp Mühlmatte.

The municipalities in the Gürbe catchment rely on groundwater and spring water for their water supply. The drinking water source of every municipality¹² lies within the catchment borders. The main sources of drinking water are in the Gurnigel area, above Blumenstein. In addition, groundwater from the valley floor and water from springs along the Längenberg are the main supplies. The regional wastewater treatment plant is located in Kaufdorf and treats wastewater from 13 neighbouring municipalities. The treated water is returned to the Gürbe.

5.2 Input Variables Water Stress Index

5.2.1 Irrigation Water Need

Here, annual irrigation and evapotranspiration data are presented, as well as monthly irrigation demands.

(Crop) evapotranspiration is the basis for calculating irrigation water demand. A Graph (Figure 16) displaying the annual values is therefore included in this results chapter for completeness. The annual values are not commented on further.

Figure 16: Annual (Crop-)Evapotranspiration values across different periods and RCP-scenarios.

12. Except for the supply of the municipality of Wald, of which only a fraction lies in the catchment area of the Gürbe.

The monthly irrigation data (Figure 17) shows that irrigation needs are highest during the summer months (June, July, and August), with significant increases projected for future periods. In the medium-term (2045–2074), the projected difference in irrigation needs, especially during the summer months, begin to accentuate themselves across the different RCP pathways, especially between the RCP 2.6 scenario and the other scenarios.

Figure 17: Average Monthly Irrigation needs (median and $Q_{0.15}$ - $Q_{0.85}$ range).

Under RCP2.6, summer peaks are projected to reach around 4 mm by 2045–2074, with an increase primarily occurring in July, although the peak happens in the preceding period. In contrast, under RCP4.5, the July peak nearly reaches 5 mm by the medium-term, with rising water demands observed across all months, particularly in June and August. For RCP8.5, summer peaks reach around 5 mm by 2045-2074, with increasingly variable results during the summer months. For the short-term period (2020–2045), RCP8.5 model chains predict lower irrigation water needs than those under RCP4.5.

The annual irrigation need (Figure 18) reveals a consistent increase in irrigation water requirements over time for all scenarios. This trend highlights the increasing demand for irrigation water due to climate change and its potential impacts on agricultural practices.

Figure 18: Projected annual irrigation water need, represented as the water column over irrigated areas in millimeters.

Under an RCP 2.6 scenario, irrigation needs rise slightly from approximately 280 mm to above 300 mm for the short-term period, and then dip again below this threshold for the medium-term period (2045–2074). Under RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenario, both scenarios show similar trends in increasing irrigation demand. While for the short-term, the 300 mm threshold is approximately reached, it is well exceeded for the 2045–2074 period, with the median values breaking the 350 mm barrier.

5.2.2 Livestock Water Need

Figure 19: Nr. of animal heads in catchment (blue: observed; orange: extrapolated).

The [Figure 19](#) illustrates the projected number of animal heads for the different livestock categories from 1980 to 2080. The combined number of livestock units decreases slightly over time, with approx. 13'000 units projected in 2080 and 13'500 in 2020, starting with approx. 16'500 units in 1980 (1980–2020: observed data).

Table 5: Projected number of total livestock units and the corresponding monthly water need in mm.

Period	No. of Livestock Units	Monthly water need [mm]
1990–2019	14'663	0.42
2020–2049	13'470	0.39
2045–2074	12'980	0.37

5.2.3 Drinking Water Need

Table 6: Projected number of residents in the Gürbe catchment and the corresponding monthly water need.

Period	No. of Residents	Monthly Water Need [mm]
1990–2019	19'020	0.70
2020–2049	21'900	0.81
2045–2074	22'757	0.84

The number of residents increases steadily over time, starting from 17'147 in 1990 and reaching 23'073 by 2070. This corresponds to a growth rate of 4.3 % per 10-year period. Concurrently, the monthly water need shows an increasing trend, rising from 0.70 mm in the observed period to 0.84 mm in the medium-term.

5.2.4 Industry Water Need

Table 7: Projected number of FTE's in the Gürbe catchment for the second and third sector and the corresponding monthly water need.

Period	FTE's (2 nd sector)	FTE's (3 rd sector)	Monthly Water Need (both sectors) [mm]
1990–2019	1'463	2'265	0.29
2020–2049	1'297	2'982	0.29

Period	FTE's (2 nd sector)	FTE's (3 rd sector)	Monthly Water Need (both sectors) [mm]
2045–2074	1'319	3'130	0.29

The FTEs in the second sector decrease from 1'463 in 1990–2019 to 1'319 in 2045–2074. Conversely, the FTEs in the third sector show an increasing trend, rising from 2'265 to 3'130 by the medium-term. Although the total number of FTE's increases, the water use remains steady, since water intensive 2nd sector jobs decrease.

5.2.5 Ecology Water Demand

Because the ecological water demand depends on the distribution of streamflow values, the demand (required residual flow) varies slightly depending on the RCP scenario and period. The resulting values are shown in the Table below.

Table 8: Ecological water demand (monthly) for the different time periods and RCP scenarios (values in mm catchment-wide).

Period	RCP 2.6	RCP 4.5	RCP 8.5
1990–2019	7.76	7.76	7.76
2020–2049	6.13	5.83	6.03
2045–2074	5.83	5.43	5.43

5.2.6 Water Availability

The projected streamflow generally follows a similar seasonal pattern to the current observed streamflow regime, but with marked differences in magnitude. In particular, the monthly peak flows in May and June tend to be lower than the values for the observed period in all projections. During the summer months (July through September), the projections suggest a significant reduction in streamflow compared to the observed period, especially for the RCP 4.5 and 8.5 scenarios. In contrast, the projected winter months (November to December) show a slight increase in streamflow. With respect to the range of uncertainties, the projections reflect the general trend of reduced summer flows and increased winter flows.

Figure 20: Comparison of streamflow regimes under the three RCP scenarios. The uncertainty range marks the quantiles $Q_{0.15}$ and $Q_{0.85}$. The gray line is the modelled streamflow of the period 1990–2019.

The median annual modelled streamflow for the observed period from 1990 to 2020 was 810 m^3 . Projections for the future period (2045–2074) show different changes in streamflow depending on the scenario. Under RCP 2.6, a slight reduction is projected (783 m^3). Under RCP 4.5, however, a more significant decrease is expected, with the average streamflow dropping to 751 m^3 . The most substantial decrease occurs under RCP 8.5, where the average streamflow declines to 746 m^3 .

5.2.7 Summary Water Availability & Demand

In summary, the demand for water for industry and livestock will not increase substantially because it depends more on the number full-time equivalents and livestock than on climate change. The demand for drinking water is expected to increase slightly as the catchment population grows. The theoretical irrigation demand will increase significantly as climate change continues, especially for the RCP 4.5 and 8.5 scenarios. Especially during the late summer months, increasing crop water demand is projected. The ecology water demand is projected to decrease because the quantity required depends on the distribution of streamflow values. As lower streamflow values become more frequent, the values decrease.

Projected water availability shows lower monthly peak flows in May and June, along with significant reductions during the summer months, especially under an RCP 4.5 and 8.5 scenario. Winter streamflow is expected to increase slightly, with uncertainties indicating a general trend of reduced summer flows and increased winter flows.

5.3 Water Stress Index

5.3.1 Monthly Water Stress Index

The graphs [Figure 21](#) and [Figure 22](#) compare the future streamflow and water demand projections with historical data (1990–2019). The graphs visualise both flow variability and demand, and show the current and future state of water stress. The depicted variability represents the Quantiles $Q_{0.15}$ and $Q_{0.85}$. The text describing the graphs refers to medium-term graph ([Figure 22](#)) that marks a continuation of the trends projected for the short-term period ([Figure 21](#)).

Figure 21: Monthly WSI-Level for the short-term period (2020–2049), compared to current stress levels. The variability range shows the $Q_{0.15}$ – $Q_{0.85}$ range.

Under an RCP 2.6 scenario, the streamflow remains relatively similar to the historical period (1990–2019). The dashed line representing future streamflow projections closely follows the historical trend, with only slight decreases in the peak flow months (April to June). Correspondingly, the water stress index is consistently low, remaining in the "no stress" (<0.1) and "low stress" (0.1–0.2) categories throughout the year as demand remains close to current levels.

In contrast, the RCP 4.5 scenario shows more noticeable shifts: While streamflow still follows a similar seasonal pattern, there is a more pronounced reduction in peak flows during the spring and early summer, with streamflow dropping below historical averages. The water stress index reflects this change, with July and August showing "moderate stress" WSI levels. Considering the variability range, the graph depicts possible (surface-)water conflicts, especially for summer months with high demand and low water availability. The increase in demand during the summer months is relatively small compared to the reduced water availability.

The RCP 8.5 scenario largely corresponds to the RCP 4.5 scenario for the medium-term, but with even an even stronger reduction in late summer streamflow. The WSI levels for the months of July and August reach the "moderate" stress state. Similar to the RCP 4.5 scenario, the variability range of the demand, including the residual water requirements, combined with the decreasing late-summer water availability, give an outlook on future periods with low water availability during the late summer months. This is mainly due to reduced water availability, as demand is increasing only slightly.

5.3.2 Distribution of monthly WSI values

Figure 23: Histogram of projected WSI-values (single months across all models). The transparent bars represent the WSI-values with the ecology water need, the solid bars the WSI-values without the ecology water need (n corresponds to [Figure 24](#)).

Figure 24: Scatterplot of projected WSI-values (total water need; single months across all models).

nate, and the number of months exceeding the 10 mm demand level are significantly reduced. The graph shows how the ecological water demand (minimum demand level) decreases as the flow duration curve of the Gürbe River changes due to changing flow patterns with climate change.

Analyzing the distribution of WSI values for the summer months only (Figure 25), the trends found in the annual distributions are repeated, but with a significantly higher number of months with WSI values in the high stress ranges. The histogram shows that summer months with very scarce water resources won't be a rarity, but can be significantly reduced if an RCP 2.6 scenario is achieved.

Figure 25: Histogram of projected WSI-values for summer months (single months across all models). The transparent bars represent the WSI-values with the ecology water need, the solid bars the WSI-values without the ecology water need.

If only the water uses are considered that generally rely on surface water resources, WSI-values indicating high-stress levels become less frequent compared to total water need WSI-values. The distribution of surface water WSI values shows that throughout the year, the months in which demand can be met clearly dominate. However, especially under the RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios, months with higher surface water WSI values occur more frequently.

Figure 26: Histogram of projected WSI-values for surface water (single months across all models; n corresponds to [Figure 24](#)).

5.3.3 Yearly WSI-values

The period medians of the total annual water demand WSI values show a steady increase for the RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios. They increase similarly over time, with both scenarios reaching a WSI of 0.1 in the 2045–2074 period. This corresponds to a low level of water stress. When ecology is considered as a demand, this level increases to a moderate stress state, with WSI reaching up to 0.27. Under the RCP 2.6 scenario, the annual WSI values in the catchment are projected to remain steady.

Table 9: Annual water stress index values across all periods and RCP-scenarios. The values in the brackets indicate the WSI, if ecology is considered in the demand.

Period	RCP 2.6	RCP 4.5	RCP 8.5
1990–2020	0.07 (0.26)	0.07 (0.26)	0.07 (0.26)
2020–2049	0.08 (0.24)	0.08 (0.24)	0.08 (0.24)
2045–2074	0.08 (0.24)	0.1 (0.25)	0.1 (0.27)

Figure 27: Scatterplot of projected annual WSI-values (water need without ecology; single years across all models).

The distribution of possible annual WSI values (see [Figure 27](#)), taking into account all individual years across all models, shows that there are clear differences between the scenarios. For example, under an RCP 2.6 scenario, years in which the "low stress" state is reached are an exception, and the two "moderate stress" values clearly mark outliers when looking at the scatterplot. Even under an RCP 4.5 scenario, years with "moderate" water stress levels still mark rather exceptional years, but the scatterplot shows that the number of years with low water availability and higher theoretical water demand is increasing, which is also reflected in more frequent "low stress" values. This trend is even more pronounced under an RCP 8.5 scenario, where years within the "low stress" bracket become very common. These findings are also represented in the corresponding histogram ([Figure 28](#))

Figure 28: Histogram of projected yearly WSI-values (single years across all models). The transparent bars represent the WSI-values with the ecology water need, the solid bars the WSI-values without the ecology water need (n corresponds to [Figure 27](#)).

5.3.4 Summary of yearly and monthly trends

Overall, the analysis of the monthly and annual WSI values indicates that while water stress will generally remain low under the RCP 2.6 scenario, more severe outcomes are projected under the RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios. Under these scenarios, the summer months will regularly experience significant water stress, particularly in July and August. The distribution of future monthly WSI values shows that there will be months where theoretical demand exceeds supply. This is mainly due to reduced summer streamflow. On an annual scale, the long-term annual WSI values indicate a slight increase (RCP 4.5 & RCP 8.5), but do not predict a state of water stress. However, years with extreme conditions (very low streamflow; high demand) may still occur, especially under low mitigation scenarios. Years exceeding the "high stress" threshold are not projected.

5.4 Findings from Interviews

This section summarizes the findings of the interviews. A list of the interviewees can be found in section [4.3](#). The findings from the interviews are written in the present tense and not as indirect speech. Nevertheless, they are the statements of the interviewed representative of the organization quoted in the subsequent short quotations. If no citation is given after a statement, the statement is from the same interview as the first subsequent citation. The interview findings are organized by topic.

5.4.1 Hydrology

According to the representative of the Fisheries Inspectorate, the Gürbe has already changed to a pure rainwater catchment area. Due to the reduced snowfall, there are increased runoff peaks in the late fall and winter months. On the other hand, in past summers there have been an increasing number of phases with very low discharges values following dry periods. This is strongly reflected in the tributaries in the southwest of the catchment area, as these dry out quickly (namely the Fallbach and Tannhölzligaben, as well as other tributaries in this area). The low water volumes, combined with the heat, lead to very high water temperatures. Only in the Müsche and the adjacent side streams, cold water regularly emerges from the drainage pipes, ensuring generally cold water temperatures. In general, the Müsche has a more con-

stant discharge than the Gürbe during the dry summers (Fischereiinspektorat Kanton Bern, 2024). The representatives of the Wasserbauverband also report increasing floods after continuous rainfall, in contrast to the “classic” floods after thunderstorms in the Gurnigel region (WBV Untere Gürbe und Müsche, 2024).

5.4.2 Irrigation

For irrigation purposes, groundwater and surface water resources are used in the Gürbetal (Blattenheid Trinkwasserversorgung, 2024; WBV Untere Gürbe und Müsche, 2024)¹³. Agricultural irrigation is not widespread and only applied selectively during critical growth periods (e.g., shortly after sowing or shortly before harvest). In addition, only crops for which it is ecologically worthwhile are irrigated (vegetables, berries, occasionally maize). Cereal irrigation is not economically feasible at present. Irrigation of pastures and meadows is also not profitable and is therefore not practiced on a large scale. Irrigation is done with hose or sprinkler systems. Drip irrigation is not used at present, or only in isolated cases. My interviewees were not aware of any increased investment in irrigation infrastructure or drought insurances in the catchment area (WBV Untere Gürbe und Müsche, 2024).

Permits for the use of surface water are issued by the municipalities, while groundwater extraction and water extraction with fixed infrastructure require a concession, issued by the canton. In the event of low streamflow values, the cantonal government (the regional governor's office¹⁴) may impose a ban on water abstraction. In recent hot summers, such bans have been issued (WBV Untere Gürbe und Müsche, 2024). Compliance with the ban is monitored by, among others, the Fisheries Inspectorate (Fischereiinspektorat Kanton Bern, 2024). As an alternative, water from the public drinking water supply is sometimes used in consultation with the local water supplier (WBV Untere Gürbe und Müsche, 2024). Local water suppliers sometimes issue instructions not to irrigate at the same time as peak domestic demand occurs (Blattenheid Trinkwasserversorgung, 2024). The canton states that drinking water always has priority over irrigation water use (AWA Abteilung Trinkwasser, 2024).

13. One of the representatives of the WBV Untere Gürbe & Müsche is a farmer. Therefore, I also asked him about local agricultural practices (i.e. irrigation).

14. der/die Statthalter/in

During the summer, surface waters (Gürbe and tributaries) are often used by private individuals to irrigate their private gardens. These water abstractions are often illegal. This, combined with the mostly permitted agricultural irrigation, has already increasingly contributed to undercutting the legally prescribed residual water quantity (Fischereiinspektorat Kanton Bern, 2024).

With regard to agriculture, the increased occurrence of heavy rainfall and the succession of dry and wet years were also mentioned as a general problem during the interviews. Regarding local impacts of droughts, peat degradation, which is accelerated by dry periods, was mentioned. Heat, regardless of droughts, was furthermore mentioned as a challenge (WBV Untere Gürbe und Müsche, 2024).

5.4.3 Livestock

Due to hygiene regulations, drinking water from the public network is often used in stables, as regular checks of local wells are costly. In many cases, however, cattle also have access to a well on the pasture that is fed from a local spring (WBV Untere Gürbe und Müsche, 2024). The cattle's water needs are therefore met by spring water and water from the public drinking water supply.

5.4.4 Ecology

Of all the water users represented by the consumption categories, ecology was most affected during the past drought periods. In addition to the low water volumes, the high temperatures also played a decisive role. This aspect in particular, in addition to the drying up of many tributaries, led to large-scale fish mortality in the Gürbe. In the summer of 2022, the Gürbe, which is still known among fishermen for its brown trout, reached up to 26°C (site: Mühlethurnen). For brown trout, conditions are precarious from 18–19°C and end in certain death from 24°C onwards. For this reason, more than half of the stock died in the summer of 2022. While the Gürbe used to be extensively stocked with brown trout, today the focus is more on targeted species conservation. The stocking takes place in side streams that are known to be cold. Other traditional Gürbe fish are also suffering from the high temperatures, such as the European bullhead. Increased flooding during the late fall and winter months also means that more spawning pits are buried or washed away. Since the Gürbe is accessible to fish from the Aare, new fish species are taking over the habitat. Today, for example, the Gürbe is home to more heat-resistant white fish that come up from the Aare. Overall, it is possible that the fish biomass is now almost higher than before the dry summers, due to the shoals of white fish.

Other changes observed in the Gürbe include a downward trend in the macrobenthic population and increased algal formation. However, these changes are also related to water quality. This is a concern in the Gürbe catchment due to the intensively used agricultural environment (Fischereiinspektorat Kanton Bern, 2024).

5.4.5 Drinking water

The drinking water supply in the Gürbe Valley was always guaranteed, even in the summers of 2018 and 2022 (AWA Abteilung Trinkwasser, 2024). Only in non-networked, local spring catchments for drinking water use, local supply bottlenecks occurred due to reduced spring discharges. This also led to local calls for water conservation (general calls; shutting down running wells); (AWA Abteilung Trinkwasser, 2024; Blattenheid Trinkwasserversorgung, 2024).

A total of 8 municipalities (total: 19) in the Gürbe catchment area are connected to the "Blattenheid" water supply. The water supply provides a total of 19 regional municipalities with water. Most of the water comes from the "Blattenheid" spring in the Homad area (in the Gürbe catchment area). The water association additionally draws groundwater from the Stockental valley near Oberstocken. The flow rate of the Blattenheid spring is strongly dependent on precipitation and decreases noticeably after about three weeks with little precipitation. However, the level has never fallen below 2000 l/min, even during past droughts. This source output level is required to operate the connected drinking water power plant in Blumenstein. The groundwater level at the pumping station in Oberstocken shows strong fluctuations (15–20 m), but during a test run in winter (at low water levels) it was still possible to withdraw twice the concessioned amount. In order to cover possible peak days and to bridge bottlenecks, the water supply systems of Blattenheid (and also of Belp), which together cover a significant part of the municipalities in the Gürbe catchment area, are connected to neighboring water supply systems. These draw water from the Aare groundwater body and from the Emmental. Normally, the Gürbetal utilities feed their surplus water into the connected neighboring supply systems to save pumping energy; however, in the event of local water shortages in the Gürbetal, groundwater from the Aare valley can be used to bridge potential shortages (Blattenheid Trinkwasserversorgung, 2024). The resilience of the connected drinking water supply in the Gürbetal is considered to be very high, while the unconnected local spring water supplies may occasionally experience supply shortages (AWA Abteilung Trinkwasser, 2024; Blattenheid Trinkwasserversorgung, 2024).

It is not known whether climate change will reduce the discharge of regional springs in the long term. The Canton of Bern has not yet conducted a regional assessment. However, due to increased evaporation and decreasing soil water balance, as well as less precipitation in summer, it is expected that the water input into the groundwater will be reduced, at least in phases. In particular, summer is the most critical phase in this respect, as this is when demand is at its highest. The demand for drinking water increases dramatically on very hot days (AWA Abteilung Trinkwasser, 2024). For example, the total water demand of the Blattenheid water supply increases 1.5–1.8 times on a hot summer day compared to a normal day (Blattenheid Trinkwasserversorgung, 2024). The Canton of Bern is currently developing a concept to examine the resilience of its water supply. To this end, a balance is being drawn up between the security of supply and the peak day. In terms of security of supply, if the most important supply point fails, at least the average demand must still be covered. On the peak day, the maximum demand must be covered by the minimum supply. Based on this, the need for action is defined, also with regard to water procurement and technical measures. The possible development of new sources would be difficult. At present, the canton's main objective is to connect or merge water supplies in order to alleviate regional bottlenecks (AWA Abteilung Trinkwasser, 2024).

5.4.6 Summary Interviews

The interviews revealed that climate change has already affected the availability of water resources and aquatic ecosystems in the Gürbe catchment. Periods of high heat and low streamflow have significantly altered the Gürbe's fish assemblage, and caused mass mortality. The interviews provided insight into local agricultural practices. Irrigation is not practiced on a large scale. It is only applied intermittently during critical growth periods. Both surface and groundwater resources are used for irrigation. Livestock water needs are generally met by public drinking water supplies and local springs. Illegal water withdrawals for private use have contributed to further undercutting residual water levels during dry periods. Drinking water supplies that are interconnected with neighboring facilities are very stable and resilient during droughts. Local water supplies that are not interconnected and rely on tapped springs may experience reduced production during dry periods. Whether regional groundwater and spring water resources in general will have reduced output due to climate change is not known.

6 Discussion

6.1 Summary of the results

The results chapter outlines water stress projections for the Gürbe catchment, highlighting changes in water demand and availability under different climate change scenarios.

The results of this thesis show that irrigation is projected to increase significantly under climate scenarios RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5, driven by rising temperatures and reduced summer precipitation. Irrigation demand peaks during the summer months, with annual irrigation demand exceeding 20 mm (catchment-wide) in the medium term (2045–2074). Livestock water demand, on the other hand, is projected to decrease slightly due to a reduction in livestock numbers. Domestic water demand is projected to increase steadily, driven by population growth. By the medium-term, domestic water demand is expected to increase from 8.5 mm to 10 mm per year (catchment-wide). Industrial water demand remains stable as a shift away from water-intensive activities offsets the increasing number of full-time equivalents. Ecological water demand is expected to decrease slightly as streamflow diminishes.

Water availability is projected to suffer, with significant reductions during the (late) summer under the RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios. Winter streamflow is expected to rise slightly, but the overall trend indicates a reduction of annual streamflow under all RCP-scenarios.

The average monthly Water Stress Index (WSI) indicates moderate stress in the summer months under higher climate change scenarios, particularly in July and August. Water stress in these months are projected to occur frequently in future years. Increasing WSI values are primarily caused by decreasing water availability. Annual WSI values remain low, although they increase from 0.07 to 0.1 (excluding ecology) for the RCP 4.5 and 8.5 scenarios.

The results of the interviews support these projections and show that real impacts are already being felt in the Gürbe catchment. Agricultural irrigation is practised, but not extensively, yet water abstraction has been constrained during the past droughts of 2018 and 2022. Ecological systems are particularly affected, with fish populations declining and changing due to higher temperatures and reduced summer flows.

Despite these challenges, the water supply systems in the Gürbe Valley have proven resilient, ensuring consistent access to water even during past droughts, with the exception of some local, unconnected spring water sources that have experienced shortages.

6.2 Water demand

6.2.1 Irrigation

Irrigation is the most important demand sector, representing the largest quantities (except for ecology), as well as the largest increase in demand over the periods.

The methodology used to obtain the irrigation demand has already been used in studies with a similar scope (see Milano et al., 2016). The approach is a strong simplification, as soil water processes are only superficially considered, and the irrigation efficiency is assumed to be 100%. This is never the case, as there is always a loss of water in rain fed irrigation systems. Efficiency usually varies with the growth stage of the irrigated crop. Furthermore, no effective precipitation was calculated to consider the proportion of rainfall that contributes to meeting crop water needs. Ice and snow processes were ignored. These two factors were not taken into account, as the aim was to provide an estimate of future total demand for an overall water balance calculation, rather than to calculate precise future irrigation requirements for agricultural purposes. Irrigation was calculated throughout the year. Often irrigation is only calculated for the period March–October (see Brunner et al., 2019a; Smith and Fuhrer, 2015). However, the calculated demand for December–February is almost zero. Therefore, calculating demand over the whole year and ignoring snow and ice processes does not affect the results.

In this thesis, irrigation is initiated, if the crop water demand exceeds the mean precipitation over the last seven days. This marks an oversimplification, as water retention capacities heavily depend on the properties of local soils. However, if only the daily difference was used (like i.e. in Milano et al., 2016), the irrigation demand would have been heavily overestimated, since irrigation is not practiced after one day without rain.

Another way to represent catchment wetness is through a continuous precipitation index, as used by Brunner et al. This method takes into account water demand based on the length of dry periods—prolonged droughts increase demand, while short ones don't. Smith and Fuhrer (2015) take a more detailed approach, triggering irrigation only when actual evapotranspiration falls below 80% of the potential, considering root depth and soil properties. Eisenring et al. (2021) further include infiltration capacity and soil porosity, with irrigation starting when soil moisture drops below a crop-spe-

cific threshold for water stress. Generally, publications focusing on agriculture, tend to implement more sophisticated irrigation calculations (Eisenring et al., 2021; Fuhrer, 2012; Fuhrer and Holzkämper, 2013; Smith and Fuhrer, 2015), while hydrological publications often times rely on simplified approximations that don't take specific soil properties into account (Brunner et al., 2019a; Milano et al., 2016).

The dominant agricultural soil types in the Gürbe catchment have a high water holding capacity. The usable field capacity of peat soils is high to very high (100–240 mm; Scheffer et al., 2018, p. 496). The values increase with the proportion of organic materials in the soil. As peat soils degrade, their proportion of organic substance decreases. Peat soil can shrink heavily during droughts, which leads to reduced water retention capacity and sometimes even hydrophobic behaviour (Naasz et al., 2008). Gürbetal peat soils are severely degraded (Kanton Bern, 2017; WBV Untere Gürbe und Müsche, 2024) thus their water retention capacity is limited. The usable field capacity of Luvisols and brown earths also is high to very high (Scheffer et al., 2018). Soils with high field capacity are not very sensitive to drought capacity (Scheffer et al., 2018). Considering the soil properties, the "water retention time" of seven days chosen in this thesis may not accurately represent the usable water retention capacity of the regional soils and may be an underestimate. Choosing a ten-day precipitation timespan to define catchment wetness would have led to a decrease of the annual irrigation needs by 16% for the present and 13% for the medium term (RCP 8.5). For a 14-day timespan, the decrease would have been 27% (present) and 22% (medium-term, RCP 8.5). This in turn could correspond to an underestimation of demand, which is why the 7-day time window was kept.

For the annual evapotranspiration values, the calculated values agree with the literature. In the Table below, the annual evapotranspiration values from Smith and Fuhrer (2015) are compared with my values. Smith & Fuhrer used the Turc equation. The reference scenario describes the period 1981–2010 (this thesis: 1990–2019), while the future values project the demand for the medium term (2045–2074). The values agree very well and show a similar magnitude of increase.

Table 10: Comparison of annual PET-values (values in mm).

	Smith & Fuhrer (2015; BE)	This thesis
Reference	654	690
Mild CC / RCP 2.6	695	713
Strong CC / RCP 8.5	734	746

The water column over the irrigated area calculated in this thesis is tending to be high. In the Table below, annual irrigation values from Smith and Fuhrer (2015) are compared to my values for potatoes. The values presented by Smith & Fuhrer are for clay loam soils (110cm). The values from Eisenring et al. (2021) are aggregated from different soil types.

Table 11: Comparison of potato irrigation need (values in mm).

	Smith & Fuhrer (BE)	Eisenring (BE)	This thesis
Reference	85	150	175
Mild CC / RCP 2.6	105	165	185
Strong CC / RCP 8.5	150	180	215

The Table shows that the calculation of the irrigation demand in this thesis is too high. For maize and sugar beets, the overestimations of irrigation requirements are even more pronounced. The values calculated for these crops exceed Smith & Fuhrer's¹⁵ values by a factor of 2 to 3. Because the total annual water need of these crops does not differ in the same magnitude as the difference in the total annual irrigation need, the overestimation can most likely be attributed to the lacking consideration of the increased rooting depth of these crops. Even when comparing the values to soil types with a reduced usable field capacity that may more accurately represent the degraded peat soil, the irrigation demand estimates by Smith & Fuhrer turn out significantly lower than in this thesis. A slight contribution to the high irrigation requirements is made by the higher evapotranspiration rates (see [Table 10](#)). Generally, the irrigation water column over the irrigated area is overestimated. This is most likely due to the oversimplification of soil water processes.

The comparison of the monthly irrigation demand curve in this study agrees well with the findings in the literature, showing a peak in July, along with increased demand in June and August. While some sources differ on the exact timing of peak water demand for specific crops, the results of this thesis did not reveal any significant anomalies in the monthly irrigation demand patterns. The crop coefficient approach, combined with regionally adjusted growth length data, provides a stable representation of the seasonal variability of crop water requirements.

15. These crops are not included in Eisenring et al., (2021).

The total irrigation water need¹⁶ is low, compared to Brunner et al. (2019a). Brunner et al. estimate a daily water need between 0.09 and 0.16 mm (present period). In this thesis, the daily irrigation demand is 0.04 mm (1990–2019). This could be because only vegetable, maize, and orchard cropping areas were considered as irrigated. It is not clear, what area types were considered as irrigated in Brunner et al. (2019a) and what the irrigation water column would be for the irrigated area only. In Brunner et al. (2019a), the irrigation requirement for the Gürbe catchment area¹⁷ is 1.5 to 4 times higher than in my thesis.

When comparing the methodology of this thesis with the interview input of the local farmer, the irrigation levels are likely overestimated. According to him, irrigation is used sparingly and only at certain stages of crop growth. Furthermore, only those crops for which irrigation is economically viable are irrigated. This factor is considered in this thesis, as only certain cropping areas were considered for irrigation. However, it is very likely that even for these sections, irrigation is overestimated, as irrigation is not applied continuously and extensively, and no equipment is pre-installed. This means that soil water deficits are unlikely to be compensated immediately if, for example, rain is forecast for the next few days. Water stress due to reduced irrigation does not lead to the instant death of the plant. For example, if only 40–50% of water of the usable field capacity in a soil is retained over longer periods of time during the primary growing season, a significant decline in yield is expected, but not crop failure (Scheffer et al., 2018). For this reason, whether irrigation is practiced is, among other factors, dependent on economic reasons. Nevertheless, the interviews showed that irrigation is common practice in the catchment.

The agricultural land use in this study is assumed to remain stable over the examined timeframe. However, this assumption does not reflect the reality, as climate change is expected to alter crop patterns, either through shifts in agricultural policy or through a natural shift to more climate-resilient crops (Lanz, 2021; WBV Untere Gürbe und Müsche, 2024). These crops will need to be more resistant not only to drought but also to heavy rainfall periods. In the Gürbetal region, agricultural practices face additional challenges. Degraded peat soils may necessitate a reduction in cultivation intensity on the valley floor, and many drainage systems are approaching the end of their operational life (Kanton Bern, 2017; WBV Untere Gürbe und Müsche, 2024). In the medium to long term, even the rewetting of peatlands could become a viable option due to increasingly limited management opportunities in these areas

16. Not the water column over the irrigated area but the water column over the entire catchment

17. In Brunner et al., the results are broken down by catchment area, so that the calculated demand for the Gürbetal can be analysed.

(see Guenat, 2022). This contrasts with national trends such as the expansion of vegetable cultivation and greenhouse farming (Lanz, 2021; OECD, 2023). The precise impact of these regional challenges and national trends on the regional agriculture in the Gürbetal remains uncertain and is beyond the scope of this study to predict.

In summary, the methodology used to calculate irrigation demand is likely to overestimate the water column over irrigated areas. This is due to an oversimplification of soil water processes. Furthermore, the approach assumes continuous and extensive irrigation, which is not practised in reality. Nevertheless, the total irrigation water demand is lower than in comparable studies. This is because only part of the agricultural area was assumed to be irrigated. This shows that the choice of crops to be considered irrigated has a much greater impact on the total water needed than the methodology used to calculate crop-specific irrigation requirements. The monthly pattern of the irrigation demand is consistent with literature. Taking these factors into account, the results presented provide a plausible estimate of irrigation requirements.

6.2.2 Livestock and Ecology

The multiplication of the number of livestock in a catchment with the daily water need per animal is common practice to calculate livestock water demand (Alcamo et al., 1997; Brunner et al., 2019a; Milano et al., 2016). The daily water need per livestock unit by Freiburghaus (2009) is higher than numbers suggested in other publications with an international scope (i.e. Alcamo et al., 1997). The numbers of Freiburghaus however, are most likely more accurate, as they are deduced from data of the Swiss water supplier's association. The future number of livestock, like irrigation demand, will be influenced by agricultural policies and consumer trends. The projections in this study are based on current European trends, but their realization remains uncertain.

The ecological water demand projected for future periods in this study may be underestimated, depending on how frequently residual water requirements are updated in response to climate change as streamflow patterns shift. Generally, the calculation of residual water requirements is not subject to significant uncertainty, as it follows clear legal regulations.

6.2.3 Drinking Water and Industrial Water

The population forecast in this study is based on overarching scenarios, which were scaled down to the catchment area. These scenarios naturally involve uncertainties¹⁸. This is particularly true in smaller areas, where large housing developments can have a significant impact on the population figures. However, such potential impacts are

accounted for through the consideration of cantonal area types and their respective growth scenarios. Furthermore, regional planning documents indicate (see ERT et al., 2021; RKBM, 2021) that while some areas in the catchment are designated for new housing developments, they are not extensive enough to significantly alter the forecasted population growth.

The projected tertiarization of jobs in the Gürbetal aligns with national trends, which are reflected in the Swiss wide decreasing proportion of industrial and commercial water use (Freiburghaus, 2015). Due to the small size of the area, the decline in jobs in the secondary sector could be offset by a new large industrial company, but this is unlikely. Regional planning does not allocate space for major industrial developments, and the region currently lacks significant industry. Nonetheless, the area's well-connected drinking water supplies at the entrance and exit of the valley could theoretically support such a site, although the low streamflow of the Gürbe would not be suitable for possible cooling water use. Assuming no such deviations from current trends, the future water demand for the industrial sector will likely remain within the forecasted range.

One limitation of the methodological approach, particularly for domestic water, is that consumption peaks on hot days are not captured. These peaks, caused by garden irrigation and swimming pool filling in areas with many private gardens (Lanz, 2021), are noticeable in the Gürbetal. For example, the Blattenheid drinking water supply sees demand increase by a factor of 1.5 to nearly 2 on hot days (Blattenheid Trinkwasserversorgung, 2024). Additionally, the drying up of smaller springs that feed livestock wells could further increase water demand from the public supply during droughts. However, since the results are aggregated at the monthly level, these short-term peaks should not significantly affect the overall findings. Another unaccounted factor is the gradual decline in per capita household water consumption, which, according to Freiburghaus (2009), is expected to continue until around 2030. Furthermore, it is possible that increased dry spells in Switzerland will also lead to water conservation in the home being seen as 'exemplary environmental behaviour', as is already the case in Germany (Lanz, 2021). This may lead to a further decrease in household water use. At a monthly aggregate level, these declines have little impact on the overall water demand projections and were therefore not considered.

18. The population projections for the canton of Bern in 2050 show a difference of around 14% between the low and high estimates when compared to the current population (Kanton Bern, 2021). In this thesis, the medium growth estimate was used.

6.2.4 Summary water demand

Irrigation is the largest water demand sector with the highest projected increase over time. The methodology used simplifies soil water processes, leading to overestimated water column over irrigated areas but yield plausible overall results. The monthly irrigation demand patterns are in good agreement with the literature. Livestock water demand is projected based on current agricultural trends, but future figures remain uncertain due to unknown changes in agricultural policies and consumer trends. Ecological water demand may be underestimated depending on regulatory updates in response to climate change, although calculations generally follow regulatory requirements. Projections of drinking and industrial water demand consider population growth and shifts in employment, with no significant deviations expected. Based on the considerations discussed, it can be assumed that the estimates in this study are plausible.

6.3 Water Availability

The modelled streamflow data was generated by the PREVAH hydrological model.

Figure 29: Comparison of observed and modelled streamflow over the model validation period (1985–2014) and the corresponding Pardé coefficients.

The PREVAH model can reliably simulate the Swiss hydrological cycle (see i.e. Brunner et al., 2019a; Zappa and Pfandler, 2009), which is also demonstrated by the Muelchi et al. (2022a) dataset. However, some questions arise regarding the performance of the model during low flow periods. In a study by Orth et al. (2015), comparing the HBV, PREVAH and SWBM models, it was found that the PREVAH model generally performs better in wet months than in dry months and is outperformed by the other models (months exceeding the 0.05 and 0.95 quantiles were examined). The day-to-day variability of the PREVAH model during dry months was reduced to almost

zero. In the Muelchi et al. runoff ensemble, an attempt was made to circumvent this by defining transformed discharge $((\max(Q) + \min(Q)) - Q_i)$ as one of four parameters to calibrate the model. This gives more weight to low flow values. In addition, odd years were chosen to validate the model as they include more extreme years. Since the model shows a good performance during the validation period in the Gürbe catchment ([Table 2](#)), it can reproduce extreme and changing conditions quite well.

When comparing the modelled and observed data (see [Figure 29](#)), it is evident that the model generally underestimates streamflow. The comparison between modelled and observed streamflow shows that the model captures the general seasonal patterns, but underestimates streamflow from May onwards. The uncertainty ranges show that both observed and modelled data have high variability. For the $Q_{0.85}$ values no clear pattern emerges. For the lower interval ($Q_{0.15}$), the modelled streamflow more often includes lower monthly streamflow values than the observed data. This is most pronounced in May and June but is consistent throughout the year. The comparison of the Pardé coefficients shows a good general agreement of the seasonal patterns, with the model overestimating the proportional monthly streamflow during the early part of the year (Jan–May) and slightly underestimating it during the summer and late autumn. The underestimation is most pronounced for August and November. One possible explanation for the underestimation could be that the climatic input variables do not adequately represent the microclimate in the Gurnigel area, the Gürbe source area, which is well known for severe thunderstorms.

The streamflow data from Muelchi et al. (2022a) generally provide a reliable picture of streamflow in the Gürbes and capture the main seasonal patterns well. The model performs well in reproducing extreme and changing conditions. Despite underestimating streamflow values, the overall accuracy of the model makes the data suitable for assessing water availability in the Gürbe catchment for a water stress index analysis. However, the underestimation of discharge values must be considered when interpreting the results.

6.4 Contextualisation of results

6.4.1 Comparison demand Gürbetal – Switzerland

The comparison of water demand between the Gürbe catchment and Switzerland highlights key differences in sectoral water use (see [Figure 30](#)).

Irrigation is the largest demand sector in the Gürbe catchment, and its proportional share is significantly higher than the national average. In contrast, drinking water and industrial demands remain relatively stable both across the catchment and in Switzerland. Livestock water use is minimal in both cases but significantly higher in the Gürbe catchment. Nationally, snow production, tourism and hydropower are further demand categories. They were not considered in this research, due to them not being relevant for the Gürbe catchment.

Figure 30: Comparison of water demand shares of the Gürbetal and Switzerland. Left: only categories relevant for this study; right: all water use sectors in Switzerland. Switzerland data from Brunner et al. (2019a).

Regarding the categories evaluated in this research, the differences between Switzerland and the Gürbetal can be explained with the Gürbetal being a rural area, as agricultural water use dominates.

6.4.2 Comparison of Medium-Term Streamflow Projections with the 2018 & 2022 Droughts

When comparing the lowest monthly streamflow values from the drought summers of 2018 and 2022 with the distribution of projected monthly summer values for the medium term (2045–2074; individual months across all model chains), it is evident that both summers still would be considered rather dry summers during this time period. In 2018, the month with the lowest streamflow (August) corresponds to quantile $Q_{0.11}$ under an RCP 2.6 scenario and to the $Q_{0.16}$ quantile under RCP 8.5. Similarly, in 2022, the month with the lowest streamflow (June) corresponds to $Q_{0.12}$ under RCP 2.6 and $Q_{0.17}$ values under an RCP 8.5 scenario. These quantiles may be overestimated as the model tends to underestimate streamflow (see Section 6.3). However, if we take

the distribution of monthly summer streamflow for the period 1990–2020 as a reference, the lowest monthly streamflow from 2022 falls at quantile $Q_{0.0}$. There are no lower values. The lowest value of this quantity is marked by August 2018. Therefore, while the summers of 2018 and 2022 would still be considered low-streamflow summers in the medium-term, they would not be outliers and would fall within the $Q_{0.1}$ to $Q_{0.9}$ range when analysing the Gürbe's monthly summer streamflow.

6.5 Interviews

The purpose of the interviews with the representatives listed in section 4.3, was to provide specific regional context for the quantitative results. Most of the interviews provided valuable regional information on the different water use sectors.

Interviewees expressed different views on past and future droughts in the Gürbetal. The representative of the Fisheries Inspectorate expressed the most concern. The results of the interview with him suggest that the fluvial ecosystem is already under severe pressure, threatening biodiversity. Although concerns about future extreme summers were not explicitly mentioned, it became clear that climate change is having a major impact on the work and planning of the Fisheries Inspectorate. These concerns were not shared by the WBV¹⁹ representatives. One representative, a farmer, emphasised that agriculture has a natural ability to adapt over time, even in the face of climate change. The representatives were more concerned about peatland degradation and the acceleration of this process during droughts. This concern is in accordance with literature (see Brouns et al., 2014; Guenat, 2022). In addition, the representative highlighted wider concerns about agriculture in the Gürbetal in general, the Gürbetal being a 'peripheral' area, and increasing regulatory pressures. In terms of natural hazards, it became clear that flooding is the main concern. This is not surprising as the WBV is responsible for flood protection measures and the Gürbe has a history of floods (see i.e. Salvisberg, 2017).

I observed that actors were reluctant to blame and accuse each other. For example, interviewees said that there were no 'water conflicts' when talking about water use regulations during recent dry summers, even though surface water use was restricted and illegal water abstraction took place. The agricultural WBV representatives described the water abstraction regulations as 'responsible'.

19. "Wasserbauverband"; see WBV Untere Gürbe und Müsche (see 2024).

The representatives of the drinking water sector (Cantonal Office for Waste and Water, Blattenheid Drinking Water Supply) did not mention any concerns about the water supply in the area. However, both representatives were aware of examples of municipalities with unconnected water supplies that experienced shortages during the droughts in 2018 and 2022. The cantonal representative, in particular, emphasised the importance of connected water supplies, which allow municipalities to access multiple water resources.

Overall (with the exception of the Fisheries Inspectorate interviewee), my impression was that my questions were met with a sense of surprise, as concerns about (future) droughts did not seem to interfere with the day-to-day work of the interviewees. Nevertheless, the overall aim of the interviews, to get regional context and to learn about regional challenges during past droughts in order to embed the findings, was achieved.

6.6 General considerations

6.6.1 Timestep

While high temporal resolution streamflow data are required for the analysis of flood peaks, longer observation periods are relevant for the analysis of drought processes (Tallaksen and Van Lanen, 2024). This is illustrated by the widely used metric 'NM7Q' that represents a weekly period. In this thesis, the results have been aggregated to a monthly level. This allows general trends to be identified, especially with the additional aggregation over the 30-year periods. Certainly, a finer temporal analysis of the annual cycle and the possible individual events could have resulted in a finer delineation of the annual periods in which conflicts will regularly occur (in the future). However, this lower temporal resolution would have been notional, as demand peaks in particular can vary from year to year, especially in the case of irrigation, where possible changes in management practices can complicate the situation. For this reason, aggregation on a monthly basis seems appropriate.

Monthly evaluations are mainly relevant for water use sectors that rely on surface water, as surface water availability varies throughout the year. This concerns the ecology and parts of the irrigation demand. Smaller sources can also exhibit reduced flow rates during very dry months. This can have a major impact on stand-alone drinking water supplies. The literature and interviews furthermore illustrated that the 'year' and 'day' temporal resolutions are relevant for processes linked to groundwater (in our case large parts of the public water supply). The 'day' time step is relevant for

water suppliers as they need to be able to cover possible peak days. This time step is not covered in this work. The year is relevant because climate change will mainly shift the annual cycle of groundwater recharge, while the usable volume of water in large groundwater reservoirs should remain the same (Bundesamt für Umwelt BAFU, 2021).

6.6.2 Data Aggregation & Quantiles

No models and/or outliers were excluded when aggregating the data. Nor were duplicate model chains with different spatial resolutions. This would not have made much difference due to the strong aggregation of the data. Only when looking at individual months and years it would have made sense to clean up the model ensemble, as some models are now visually more prominent in the plots than others. However, this has no effect on the forecast trend and the data still gives an idea of possible future extreme events and the distribution of future WSI values.

The quantiles $Q_{0.15}$ and $Q_{0.85}$ used in the monthly regime plots (see i.e. [Figure 22](#)) are not commonly used in the literature. However, they were chosen to provide a visual representation of potential future variability. A wider range would have made the plots difficult to interpret. I considered that including a smaller range of quantiles was preferable to omitting the quantiles altogether.

6.6.3 Streamflow as water availability

Streamflow is not the same as available water in a catchment, as the components of groundwater, soil water and evaporation are missing.

Figure 31: Schematic depiction of different Gürbetal water resources.

Nonetheless, streamflow is the only stage of the hydrological cycle where water is contained within well-defined channels, allowing precise measurement of the volumes involved (Herschy, 2009). For this reason, measured streamflow was used as a "proxy" for water availability, as is common practice in water supply and demand estimations (see Alcamo et al., 2000; Brunner et al., 2019a; Kundzewicz et al., 2007; Milano et al., 2016). Nevertheless, it is important to reflect on what is actually being compared when calculating the WSI. This is schematically depicted in [Figure 31](#).

The [Figure 31](#) shows that theoretically, water already *used* is not present anymore in the stream, thus the WSI not actually compares the *available* water with the demand, but the water that is *left over*. On the other hand, water from the public supply is assumed to be *used* in the WSI, although it is partly re-entered into the stream after being treated. However, as the hydrological model has been calibrated and validated with observed streamflow values, these processes should already be reflected to some extent in the modelled data. Still, the exact portion of the effectively available water that is being used may not be accurately represented in the WSI. Nevertheless, the WSI allows comparisons of supply and demand trends over the years and between different time periods, making it a valuable measure of water stress.

Furthermore, the differentiation between water resources is not entirely possible. No water demand sector relies solely on one water resource, as the public water supply in the Gürbetal municipalities relies on both ground- and source water. The same is true for livestock, where local source water and water from the public supply is used. Irrigation water stems from surface water bodies as well as drinking water from the public water supply. This overlap complicates the delineation of water stress phases, as multiple water resources are involved for which different timeframes are relevant in terms of their scarcity processes.

Another implicit assumption in this thesis, which is not 100% true, is that the Gürbetal catchment is a closed hydrological system. Although this is true for most of the time, 11 (out of the total of 20) municipalities are connected to water supplies that could import "foreign" water from neighbouring suppliers in case of large peaks in demand (not visualized in [Figure 31](#)).

6.7 Resultate Water stress index

Taking all these points into account, it can be stated that the results are able to show the changes in water supply and water demand in the Gürbe Valley based on different climate change scenarios.

Water stress will occur more frequently in the future, mainly during summer months. The results show that the increasing water stress levels are mainly caused by the decreasing water availability during summer months and only to a small extent by an increase in water demand. The water use sectors in the Gürbetal that contribute most to the increase in demand are irrigation and drinking water, as the other three demand categories (livestock, industrial water, and ecology) are projected to remain stable or show only slight increases. In a more urban area, the other demand categories might increase more significantly. As pressure on water resources increases during late summer months, restrictions on private and agricultural water abstraction from surface waters will not be uncommon. The increased stress levels will primarily affect fluvial ecosystems and agriculture. This is illustrated by the distribution of future WSI values for surface waters only (see [Figure 26](#)), as demand (all irrigation and ecology) could exceed surface water availability and high stress levels will not be uncommon. This process is particularly accentuated for the RCP 4.5 and 8.5 scenarios. These developments could be exemplary for agriculturally dominated catchments in pre-alpine areas that are experiencing a regime change towards virtually purely pluvial regime types. Annual water stress levels show a slight increase without reaching critical water stress levels. The distribution of all possible annual WSI values reveals that under no scenario single “high stress” years will occur, even when considering outliers. Moderate stress levels however will appear considerably more frequent under RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios, as more years with low annual streamflow will arise. This could impact groundwater recharge.

With regard to public water supplies, the main concern is for unconnected supplies that rely on spring water, as several municipalities have already experienced reduced spring flows during recent hot summers that led to calls for water conservation. The drying up of springs that rely on small local groundwater systems is in accordance with the literature (Bundesamt für Umwelt BAFU, 2021). For the suppliers relying on groundwater in the valley floor, no issues occurred during past droughts. In the long-term, the increase of the mean annual WSI-levels could result in reduced groundwater recharge. However, it is currently not known how the groundwater resources in the Gürbetal will be affected by climate change (AWA Abteilung Trinkwasser, 2024). Water supplies that can rely on two independent water sources, do not face scarcity.

6.8 Outlook

The findings of this study provide significant insights into future water demand and stress in the Gürbe catchment under varying climate change scenarios. However, several areas merit further investigation to improve the robustness and applicability of the results.

One interesting aspect would be the development of more detailed scenarios for agricultural practices for the Gürbetal. The impact of climate change on local agriculture, particularly in terms of worsening soil conditions, needs to be examined more thoroughly. Further studies could explore how agricultural policy changes and how climate change may affect irrigation practices in traditionally not extensively irrigated areas. In the context of these studies it could also be quantified how rewetting the valley floor peatlands—an area currently facing significant degradation—might alleviate surface water stress during critical late summer months.

Another topic worth exploring deeper is the future discharge rates of local springs, particularly in areas reliant on unconnected water supplies. Detailed projections of how these springs (but also the valley floor groundwater bodies) will respond to climate change, particularly in relation to groundwater recharge, are necessary to better understand the future reliability of local water resources.

A more comprehensive water stress index analysis that encompasses the entire Canton of Bern or another larger hydrographic area could furthermore provide a broader understanding of water stress dynamics. This would enable policymakers and water managers to assess water availability and demand across multiple catchments and municipalities, enhancing regional resilience planning that could better consider the resilience of interconnected water supply systems.

In conclusion, while this work provides a valuable foundation for understanding water stress in the Gürbe catchment, further research is needed to explore local spring and groundwater dynamics, agricultural shifts, and larger scale water stress index assessments. These aspects are essential for a more comprehensive understanding and contextualisation of future water stress dynamics.

7 Conclusion

The findings of this thesis highlight the significant challenges that the Gürbe catchment is expected to face in the medium term (2045–2074) due to climate change. A key concern is the reduction in water availability during the summer months. At the same time, demand is expected to increase due to growing irrigation and drinking water needs. This situation is likely to exacerbate water stress, particularly for surface water resources. Surface water resources are vital for both irrigation and fluvial ecosystems. As water availability will decrease, bans on surface water abstraction during the summer months will become more frequent, affecting agriculture. Fluvial ecosystems will come under more pressure. These changes will be most pronounced in July and August. During these months, water stress will occur regularly. Under high climate change scenarios, annual water availability in the catchment is projected to decrease. Years with WSI values above 0.4 are not projected.

This thesis furthermore illustrated the importance of diversifying water supply sources. Past droughts have demonstrated the resilience of water supply systems in municipalities that have access to multiple, independent water sources. In contrast, individual municipalities relying on single sources faced shortages during past droughts. Therefore, further expanding the connectivity of water supply systems across the region is critical to ensuring a resilient and reliable water supply, especially for municipalities that currently rely on isolated water sources.

The integration of local stakeholder perspectives through interviews helped to contextualise the quantitative findings, highlighting challenges during the drought summers of 2018 and 2022. These were stress on the fluvial ecosystem with subsequent mass mortality, peat degradation, surface water abstraction constraints and illegal water abstraction.

Future studies could expand on these findings by further investigating future trends in groundwater volumes and source outputs, as there is currently insufficient knowledge. In addition, the potential to alleviate future water stress states by rewetting the peat soils on the valley floor could be explored further, as well as its ecological implications.

The role of climate change mitigation in alleviating future water stress in the Gürbe Valley cannot be overstated. Effective mitigation efforts could significantly reduce the severity of projected water shortages by ensuring higher summer streamflow levels, thereby greatly alleviating future water stress conditions. Ensuring the long-term

stability of the Gürbe Valley's water resources will require both regional adaptation measures and global efforts to mitigate climate change. Without such action, the continuous provision of sufficient water resources in the region, and hence its agricultural productivity and ecological health, may be significantly compromised.

References

- Alcamo, J., Döll, P., Kaspar, F., Siebert, S., 1997. Global change and global scenarios of water use and availability: An application of WaterGAP1.0.
- Alcamo, J., Henrichs, T., Rösch, T., 2000. World Water in 2025: Global modeling scenario analysis for the World Commission on Water for the 21st Century (No. No 2), Kassel World Water Series. Center for Environmental Systems Research University of Kassel, Kassel.
- Allen, R., Pereira, L., Raes, D., Smith, M., 1998. FAO Irrigation and Drainage Paper No. 56: Crop Evapotranspiration, FAO Guidelines. FAO.
- Aschwanden, H., Weingartner, R., 1985. Die Abflussregimes der Schweiz. Bern.
- AWA Abteilung Trinkwasser, 2024. Fragen Interview Masterarbeit Gürbetal; Christoph Bill Fachspezialist Trinkwasserversorgung.
- Blair, K.J., Moran, D., Alexander, P., 2024. Worldviews, values and perspectives towards the future of the livestock sector. *Agric Hum Values* 41, 91–108. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10460-023-10469-9>
- Blattenheid Trinkwasserversorgung, 2024. Interview Betriebsleiter Blattenheid Trinkwasserversorgung; Volker Dölitzsch.
- Blauhut, V., Stoelzle, M., Ahopelto, L., Brunner, M.I., Teutschbein, C., Wendt, D.E., Akstinas, V., Bakke, S.J., Barker, L.J., Bartošová, L., Briede, A., Cammalleri, C., Kalin, K.C., De Stefano, L., Fendeková, M., Finger, D.C., Huysmans, M., Ivanov, M., Jaagus, J., Jakubínský, J., Krakovska, S., Laaha, G., Lakatos, M., Manevski, K., Neumann Andersen, M., Nikolova, N., Osuch, M., Van Oel, P., Radeva, K., Romanowicz, R.J., Toth, E., Trnka, M., Urošev, M., Urquijo Reguera, J., Sauquet, E., Stevkov, A., Tallaksen, L.M., Trofimova, I., Van Loon, A.F., Van Vliet, M.T.H., Vidal, J.-P., Wanders, N., Werner, M., Willems, P., Živković, N., 2022. Lessons from the 2018–2019 European droughts: a collective need for unifying drought risk management. *Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci.* 22, 2201–2217. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-22-2201-2022>
- Bormann, H., Miegel, K., Casper, M., Bronstert, A., Schumann, A., Weiler, M., 2016. Hydrologie, 1. Auflage. ed, UTB Basics. UTB; Haupt Verlag, Bern.
- Brouns, K., Verhoeven, J.T.A., Hefting, M.M., 2014. Short period of oxygenation releases latch on peat decomposition. *Science of The Total Environment* 481, 61–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2014.02.030>
- Brown, A., 2011. A Review of Water Scarcity Indices and Methodologies.

- Brunner, M.I., Björnsen Gurung, A., Zappa, M., Zekollari, H., Farinotti, D., Stähli, M., 2019a. Present and future water scarcity in Switzerland: Potential for alleviation through reservoirs and lakes. *Science of The Total Environment* 666, 1033–1047. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.02.169>
- Brunner, M.I., Farinotti, D., Zekollari, H., Huss, M., Zappa, M., 2019b. Future shifts in extreme flow regimes in Alpine regions. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* 23, 4471–4489. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-23-4471-2019>
- Brunner, M.I., Götte, J., Schlemper, C., Van Loon, A.F., 2023. Hydrological Drought Generation Processes and Severity Are Changing in the Alps. *Geophysical Research Letters* 50, e2022GL101776. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022GL101776>
- Brunner, M.I., Liechti, K., Zappa, M., 2019c. Extremeness of recent drought events in Switzerland: dependence on variable and return period choice. *Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci.* 19, 2311–2323. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-19-2311-2019>
- Brunner, M.I., Tallaksen, L.M., 2019. Proneness of European Catchments to Multiyear Streamflow Droughts. *Water Resources Research* 55, 8881–8894. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019WR025903>
- Bundesamt für Landwirtschaft BLW, 2024. Gemeinsam in Richtung einer neuen Agrarpolitik 2030 [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.blw.admin.ch/blw/de/home/politik/agrarpolitik/agrarpolitik30plus.html> (accessed 9.2.24).
- Bundesamt für Statistik, 2024. Landwirtschaftliche Strukturhebung. Bern.
- Bundesamt für Statistik BFS, 2021. Statistik der Unternehmensstruktur STATENT 2021 | Bundesamt für Statistik [WWW Document]. Statistik der Unternehmensstruktur STATENT 2021 | Bundesamt für Statistik. URL <https://www.bfs.admin.ch/news/de/2023-0275> (accessed 7.24.24).
- Bundesamt für Statistik BFS, 2020. Szenarien zur Bevölkerungsentwicklung der Schweiz und der Kantone (No. 01), Statistik der Schweiz. Bundesamt für Statistik, Neuchâtel.
- Bundesamt für Statistik BFS, 2018. Arealstatistik Schweiz 2018 [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.bfs.admin.ch/bfs/de/home/statistiken/raum-umwelt/erhebungen/area.html> (accessed 7.24.24).
- Bundesamt für Umwelt BAFU, 2023. Trockenheit im Sommer 2022: Befragung der kantonalen Gewässerschutz- und Fischereifachstellen zu Auswirkungen und Massnahmen. Bundesamt für Umwelt, Bern.
- Bundesamt für Umwelt BAFU, 2021. Auswirkungen des Klimawandels auf die Schweizer Gewässer.

- Bundesamt für Umwelt BAFU, 2020. Klimawandel in der Schweiz: Indikatoren zu Ursachen, Auswirkungen, Massnahmen, Umwelt - Zustand. Bundesamt für Umwelt, Meteo Schweiz, National Center for Climate Services (NCCS), Bern.
- Bundesamt für Umwelt BAFU, 2019. Hitze und Trockenheit im Sommer 2018.
- Demuth, S., Stahl, K., 1999. Method for Regional Classification of Streamflow Drought Series: Cluster Analysis. ARIDE (No. 1), ARIDE Technical Reports. Institute of Hydrology, University of Freiburg, Freiburg.
- Der Schweizerische Bundesrat, 1998. Landwirtschaftliche Begriffsverordnung, LBV.
- Duncan, H.P., 2019. Baseflow separation – A practical approach. *Journal of Hydrology* 575, 308–313. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2019.05.040>
- Eisenring, S., Holzkämper, A., Calanca, P., 2021. Berechnung der Bewässerungsbedürfnisse unter aktuellen und zukünftigen Bedingungen in der Schweiz. *Agroscope*. <https://doi.org/10.34776/AS107G>
- ERT, KA, OS-SA, 2021. Regionales Gesamtverkehrs- und Siedlungskonzept (RGSK) Thun-Oberland West. Entwicklungsraum Thun; Planungsregion Kandertal; Obersimmental-Saanenland, Bern.
- European Commission, 2020a. Climate change and Europe's water resources. European Commission. Joint Research Centre., LU.
- European Commission, 2020b. Future of EU livestock: How to contribute to a sustainable agricultural sector: final report. Directorate General for Agriculture and Rural Development, LU.
- Fischer, A.M., Strassmann, K.M., Croci-Maspoli, M., Hama, A.M., Knutti, R., Kotlarski, S., Schär, C., Schnadt Poberaj, C., Ban, N., Bavay, M., Beyerle, U., Bresch, D.N., Brönnimann, S., Burlando, P., Casanueva, A., Fatichi, S., Feigenwinter, I., Fischer, E.M., Hirschi, M., Liniger, M.A., Marty, C., Medhaug, I., Peleg, N., Pickl, M., Raible, C.C., Rajczak, J., Rössler, O., Scherrer, S.C., Schwierz, C., Seneviratne, S.I., Skelton, M., Sørland, S.L., Spirig, C., Tschurr, F., Zeder, J., Zubler, E.M., 2022. Climate Scenarios for Switzerland CH2018 – Approach and Implications. *Climate Services* 26, 100288. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cliser.2022.100288>
- Fischereiinspektorat Kanton Bern, 2024. Interview Fischereiaufseher Gürbe; Christian Rolli.
- Fjörke, M., Alcamo, J., 2004. European Outlook on Water Use (Final Report). Center for Environmental Systems Research University of Kassel, Kassel.
- Freiburghaus, M., 2015. Wasserverbrauch: Sinkender Wasserabsatz in Schweizer Haushalten. *Aqua & Gas* 72–79.

- Freiburghaus, M., 2009. Wasserbedarf der Schweizer Wirtschaft. GWA (Gas, Wasser, Abwasser) 12, 1001–1011.
- Fuhrer, J., 2012. Bewässerungsbedarf und Wasserdargebot unter heutigen und künftigen Klimabedingungen.
- Fuhrer, J., Holzkämper, A., 2013. Wasser und Schweizer Landwirtschaft: Das Projekt AG-WAM im Rahmen des NFP 61. Aqua & Gas.
- Fuhrer, J., Jasper, K., 2009. Bewässerungsbedürftigkeit in der Schweiz. Forschungsanstalt Agroscope Reckenholz Tänikon, Zürich.
- García-Herrera, R., Díaz, J., Trigo, R.M., Luterbacher, J., Fischer, E.M., 2010. A Review of the European Summer Heat Wave of 2003. *Critical Reviews in Environmental Science and Technology* 40, 267–306. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10643380802238137>
- Guenat, C., 2022. Aus Flachmooren entstandene entwässerte Torfböden: Landwirtschaftliche Nutzung und Torferhalt - Erfahrungen aus der Schweiz. Im Auftrag des Bundesamtes für Umwelt BAFU, Bern.
- HADES, 2015. HYDRMaps [WWW Document]. Hydrologischer Atlas der Schweiz. URL <https://hydromaps.ch/#> (accessed 2.12.24).
- Harding, R., Best, M., Blyth, E., Hagemann, S., Kabat, P., Tallaksen, L.M., Warnaars, T., Wiberg, D., Weedon, G.P., Lanen, H.V., Ludwig, F., Haddeland, I., 2011. WATCH: Current Knowledge of the Terrestrial Global Water Cycle. *Journal of Hydrometeorology* 12, 1149–1156. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JHM-D-11-024.1>
- Hersch, R., 2009. *Streamflow Measurement*, 3rd ed. Taylor & Francis, London.
- Historische Statistik der Schweiz, 2012. Daten/F.34 Vollzeitäquivalente nach Branchen und Kantone - Historische Statistik der Schweiz [WWW Document]. URL <https://hss.ch/de/2012/f/34> (accessed 7.24.24).
- IPCC, 2023. Synthesis Report of the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6). Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change.
- IPCC, 2022. Chapter 13: Europe, in: *Climate Change 2022 – Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability: Working Group II Contribution to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009325844>
- IPCC, 2008. TOWARDS NEW SCENARIOS FOR ANALYSIS OF EMISSIONS, CLIMATE CHANGE, IMPACTS, AND RESPONSE STRATEGIES (IPCC EXPERT MEETING REPORT). Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, Noordwijkerhout, The Netherlands.
- Kanton Bern, 2024. Landwirtschaftliche Kulturen 2023. (Geodaten). Amt für Geoinformation des Kantons Bern, Bern.

- Kanton Bern, 2023a. Ausgewählte Ergebnisse aus den landwirtschaftlichen Strukturdaten d. Kantons Bern [WWW Document]. Wirtschafts-, Energie- und Umweltdirektion, Amt für Landwirtschaft und Natur. URL https://www.fin.be.ch/de/start/themen/OeffentlicheStatistik/statistikportal/statistiksteckbrief.html?search-Param_id=2 (accessed 9.13.24).
- Kanton Bern, 2023b. Bevölkerungsstand und -struktur [WWW Document]. Kanton Bern. URL <https://www.fin.be.ch/de/start/themen/OeffentlicheStatistik/bevoelkerungsstatistik/bevoelkerungsstand-und--struktur.html> (accessed 7.24.24).
- Kanton Bern, 2022. Statistiken des Kantons Bern: Statistik der Unternehmensstruktur STATENT. Wirtschafts-, Energie- und Umweltdirektion, Amt für Wirtschaft, Bern.
- Kanton Bern, 2021. Bevölkerungsszenarien [WWW Document]. Kanton Bern. URL <https://www.fin.be.ch/de/start/themen/OeffentlicheStatistik/bevoelkerungsstatistik/bevoelkerungsszenarien.html> (accessed 7.24.24).
- Kanton Bern, 2017. Bodenbericht 2017. Volkswirtschaftsdirektion Amt für Landwirtschaft und Natur Fachstelle Bodenschutz, Zollikofen.
- Kundzewicz, Z.W., Mata, L.J., Arnell, N., Döll, P., Kabat, P., Sçen, Z., Shiklomanov, I., Asanuma, J., Betts, R., Cohen, S., Milly, C., Nearing, M., Prudhomme, C., Pulwarty, R., Schulze, R., van Schaik, H., Becker, A., Bruce, J., 2007. Freshwater resources and their management.
- Laaha, G., Gauster, T., Tallaksen, L.M., Vidal, J.-P., Stahl, K., Prudhomme, C., Heudorfer, B., Vlnas, R., Ionita, M., Van Lanen, H.A.J., Adler, M.-J., Caillouet, L., Delus, C., Fendekova, M., Gailliez, S., Hannaford, J., Kingston, D., Van Loon, A.F., Mediero, L., Osuch, M., Romanowicz, R., Sauquet, E., Stagge, J.H., Wong, W.K., 2017. The European 2015 drought from a hydrological perspective. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* 21, 3001–3024. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-21-3001-2017>
- Lanz, K., 2021. Auswirkungen des Klimawandels auf die Wasserwirtschaft der Schweiz, Beiträge zur Hydrologie der Schweiz. Akademie der Naturwissenschaften Schweiz SCNAT, Bern.
- MeteoSchweiz, 2023. Klimabulletin Jahr 2022 (Klimabulletin). Bern.
- MeteoSwiss, 2021a. Daily Precipitation (final analysis): RhiresD, Documentation of MeteoSwiss Grid-Data Products. Federal Office of Meteorology and Climatology MeteoSwiss.
- MeteoSwiss, 2021b. Daily Mean, Minimum and Maximum Temperature: TabsD, TminD, TmaxD, Documentation of MeteoSwiss Grid-Data Products. Federal Office of Meteorology and Climatology MeteoSwiss.

- MeteoSwiss, 2021c. Daily Relative Sunshine Duration: SrelD, Documentation of MeteoSwiss Grid-Data Products. Federal Office of Meteorology and Climatology MeteoSwiss.
- Milano, M., Reynard, E., 2022. Prospective integrated modelling of water scarcity risk in western Switzerland: lessons learned and new challenges for water security assessment. *geocarrefour* 96. <https://doi.org/10.4000/geocarrefour.18618>
- Milano, M., Reynard, E., Bosshard, N., Weingartner, R., 2016. In light of seasonal climatic and anthropogenic changes, is the Vaud canton (Switzerland) vulnerable to water stress by the medium-term? *La Houille Blanche* 102, 17–24. <https://doi.org/10.1051/lhb/2016045>
- Muelchi, R., Rössler, O., Schwanbeck, J., Weingartner, R., Martius, O., 2022a. An ensemble of daily simulated runoff data (1981–2099) under climate change conditions for 93 catchments in Switzerland (Hydro-CH2018-Runoff ensemble). *Geoscience Data Journal* 9, 46–57. <https://doi.org/10.1002/gdj3.117>
- Muelchi, R., Rössler, O., Schwanbeck, J., Weingartner, R., Martius, O., 2022b. An ensemble of daily simulated runoff data (1981–2099) under climate change conditions for 93 catchments in Switzerland (Hydro-CH2018-Runoff ensemble). *Geoscience Data Journal* 9, 46–57. <https://doi.org/10.1002/gdj3.117>
- Naasz, R., Michel, J. -C., Charpentier, S., 2008. Water repellency of organic growing media related to hysteretic water retention properties. *European J Soil Science* 59, 156–165. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2389.2007.00966.x>
- National Centre for Climate Services NCCS, 2021. Klimawandel im Kanton Bern Was geschah bisher und was erwartet uns in Zukunft?, Klimawandel in den Kantonen. National Centre for Climate Services NCCS, Bern.
- NCCS, 2021. NM7Q.
- NCCS, 2018. Climate Scenarios for Switzerland (Technical Report). National Centre for Climate Services NCCS, Zürich.
- OECD, 2023. Switzerland, Agricultural Policy Monitoring and Evaluation: Adapting Agriculture to Climate Change. OECD, Paris.
- Orth, R., Staudinger, M., Seneviratne, S.I., Seibert, J., Zappa, M., 2015. Does model performance improve with complexity? A case study with three hydrological models. *Journal of Hydrology* 523, 147–159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2015.01.044>
- Pasquier, F., Bouzelboudjen, M., Weidmann, F., 1999. Hydrogeologische Karte der Schweiz: Blatt 6 - Sarine/Saane. Hydrogeologische Karte der Schweiz.
- Pestoni, A., Marti, A., Keiser, A., 2023. Datengrundlage und künftige Datenerfassung zur landwirtschaftlichen Bewässerung in der Schweiz.

- Raskin, P., 1997. *Water Futures: Assessment of Long-range Patterns and Problems*.
- RKBM, 2021. *Regionales Gesamtverkehrs- und Siedlungskonzept (RGSK) Bern-Mittelland*. Regionalkonferenz Bern-Mittelland, Bern.
- Sabater, S., Bregoli, F., Acuña, V., Barceló, D., Elosegí, A., Ginebreda, A., Marcé, R., Muñoz, I., Sabater-Liesa, L., Ferreira, V., 2018. Effects of human-driven water stress on river ecosystems: a meta-analysis. *Sci Rep* 8, 11462. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-29807-7>
- Salvisberg, M., 2017. *Der Hochwasserschutz an der Gürbe - Eine Herausforderung für Generationen (1855–2010)*. Schwabe Verlag. <https://doi.org/10.24894/978-3-7965-3684-7>
- Scheffer, Schachtschabel, Amelung, W., Blume, H.-P., Fleige, H., Horn, R., Kandeler, E., Kögel-Knabner, I., Kretzschmar, R., Stahr, K., Wilke, B.-M., 2018. *Scheffer / Schachtschabel Lehrbuch der Bodenkunde*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-55871-3>
- Singh, S.K., Pahlow, M., Booker, D.J., Shankar, U., Chamorro, A., 2019. Towards baseflow index characterisation at national scale in New Zealand. *Journal of Hydrology* 568, 646–657. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2018.11.025>
- Smith, P., Fuhrer, J., 2015. *Ermittlung des Bewässerungsbedarfs für die Landwirtschaft (No. Anhang j)*, Expertenbericht zum Umgang mit lokaler Wasserknappheit in der Schweiz.
- Soom, M., 1999. Grundwasservorkommen im Gürbetal und Belper Becken, in: *Schweizerische Geotechnische Kommission ETH (Ed.), Hydrogeologische Karte der Schweiz: Blatt 6 - Sarine/Saane; Notice explicative, Hydrogeologische Karte der Schweiz*. pp. 86–93.
- Stahl, K., Hisdal, H., Hannaford, J., Tallaksen, L.M., Van Lanen, H.A.J., Sauquet, E., Demuth, S., Fendekova, M., Jódar, J., 2010. Streamflow trends in Europe: evidence from a dataset of near-natural catchments. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* 14, 2367–2382. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-14-2367-2010>
- Tallaksen, L.M., Van Lanen, H.A.J., 2024. *Hydrological Drought: Processes and Estimation Methods for Streamflow and Groundwater*. Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-819082-1.00009-6>
- Tripet, J., Aviolat, P., Bitterli, T., Brändli, R., Christe, R., Fracheboud, S., Frey, D., George, M., Motousek, F., 2018. *Karte Grundwasservorkommen*. Hydrogischer Atlas der Schweiz.
- Van Vuuren, D.P., Edmonds, J.A., Kainuma, M., Riahi, K., Weyant, J., 2011. A special issue on the RCPs. *Climatic Change* 109, 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-011-0157-y>

- Viviroli, D., Gurtz, J., Zappa, M., 2007. The Hydrological Modelling System PREVAH. Geographica Bernensia, CH.
- Vrtic, M., von Sury, J., Fröhlich, P., Setz, M., Forster, S., 2023. Gesamtverkehrsmodell Kanton Bern: Modellaktualisierung 2019. Kanton Bern, Bau- und Verkehrsdirektion (BVD), Bern.
- Wada, Y., Van Beek, L.P.H., Viviroli, D., Dürr, H.H., Weingartner, R., Bierkens, M.F.P., 2011. Global monthly water stress: 2. Water demand and severity of water stress. *Water Resources Research* 47, 2010WR009792. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2010WR009792>
- WBV Untere Gürbe und Müsche, 2024. Interview Wasserbauverband Untere Gürbe & Müsche; Roland Trachsel & Heinrich Wildberger.
- Zappa, M., Pfaundler, M., 2009. An optimized grid data set of mean monthly and annual runoff for Switzerland: Coupling modelled data with robust information derived from observations, in: IAHS-AISH Publication. Presented at the Symposium: Hydrology in Mountain Regions: Observations, Processes and Dynamics - 14th General Assembly of the IUGG, pp. 56–62.

A Appendix

Supplementary material on the calculation of the water stress index is available on this GitHub repository:

<https://github.com/sibuer/Master-Thesis-Simon-Buerki-Guerbe-Water-Stress>

The transcripts of the interview are available on this GitHub repository (request access via swiesimon@gmail.com):

<https://github.com/sibuer/MA-transcripts>